

PROPHET Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)

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1. Executive Summary

The PROPHET Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) on Personalised Prevention reflects on the challenges for advancing personalised prevention in healthcare. With PROPHET, we are building the foundation to achieve the **final outcome of more effective, efficient and citizen-centered preventive approaches**. After extensive literature mapping on the latest research advancements in the field and after incorporating the consortium partners' views and the stakeholders' perspectives, the SRIA identified ten challenges for the implementation of personalised prevention, including: Challenge 1: The broad scope of promotion and prevention; Challenge 2: Continuous evidence synthesis system supporting personalised prevention; Challenge 3: The PROPHET Framework implementation; Challenge 4: Data collection and integration, and Data Infrastructure; Challenge 5: Community Engagement and trust; Challenge 6: Health Professionals and Policy Makers involvement; Challenge 7: Regulatory aspects and synergy with private sector; Challenge 8: Access, Equity and Coverage; Challenge 9: Ethical, Legal, Social Issues (ELSI); Challenge 10: Changing behaviour. For each challenge, state of the art, gaps, priorities and implementation, and final considerations are detailed.

Along the development of PROPHET, personalised prevention clearly emerges as a multi-faceted field that seeks to use individual information from various domains as safely and effectively as possible. This information includes an individual's lifestyle, health records, social habits, environmental exposures over time, individual omics data, role in the community, and more. Recognizing this, PROPHET endorses and strongly promotes this comprehensive definition of personalised prevention. However, to ensure the sustainability of evidence-systematization efforts, it was decided to focus on managing omics data within this ecosystem. This strategic decision aligns with the project's positioning within the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine ecosystem. Thus, while this SRIA acknowledges the importance of these diverse domains in defining personalised interventions, it primarily concentrates on policy development efforts on investigating the omics sciences sector.

Within this defined domain, we encounter additional complexity due to the multiple areas covered by omics sciences — such as genomics, metabolomics, proteomics, radiomics, epigenomics, and more. Despite their technical differences, certain shared elements allow us to propose common considerations across these fields, particularly regarding infrastructures required for omics data use. Issues related to data collection, integration, protection, and the development of data infrastructures thus have broad relevance across omics domains (Figure 1).

In contrast, when digging deeper to seek evidence of clinical utility that could inform implementation and scaling up by healthcare systems, the situation varies. In many areas of omics, there is a clear need for new, robust association studies to support biomarker candidacy as potential tools for personalised prevention. However, genomics stands out as the most structured in terms of implementation.

Given its early entry into scientific focus compared to other omics, genomics offers the primary examples upon which PROPHET has built its considerations around clinical utility and implementability, where examples of such utility are available, albeit with limitations. These examples form the core objectives of this SRIA, including applications such as genetic testing for high risk pathogenic variants, polygenic risk scores (PRS), and pharmacogenomics. These

applications highlight the practical aims of this initiative and serve as focal points for advancing personalised prevention through clinically actionable genomics data.

In conclusion, PROPHET represents a significant step towards a future where prevention is truly personalised at all its' levels, empowering individuals to take control of their health and well-being. The SRIA outlines the major areas that must be addressed in order to fully realize the potential of personalised prevention.

Figure 1. The PROPHET ecosystem

2. Background and methodology

2.1 Definition and Vision: why is personalised prevention important?

The “*Health at a Glance: Europe*” report serves as a stark reminder of the overwhelming prevalence and impact of chronic diseases on the continent.¹ As these diseases continue to be the leading causes of morbidity and mortality, accounting for a substantial proportion of premature deaths, the burden on healthcare systems becomes increasingly apparent. Moreover, the socio-economic implications of chronic diseases, including diminished productivity and increased healthcare costs, highlight the urgency for innovative and sustainable solutions.

These elements pose a direct threat to the sustainability of European healthcare systems. The traditional reactive model of healthcare, focusing on treating established diseases, is proving to be economically unsustainable. As such, a transformative shift towards primary prevention and early diagnosis, together with more effective use of pharmacological therapy, is imperative for achieving a balance between effectiveness, efficiency and quality within the constraints of public budgets.

In the past two decades, advancements in sequencing and genotyping technologies and the integration of digital resources in healthcare have ushered in a new era of medicine. This “precision-revolution” has opened possibilities for personalised prevention, where individualised risk profiles are identified through a nuanced understanding of genetics, behavioural and socio-economic factors. By tailoring interventions based on this information, personalised prevention aims to delay disease onset, enhance quality of life and ultimately reduce the economic burden on healthcare systems. In this context, the need for a comprehensive and proactive strategy to mitigate the burden of chronic diseases is more pressing than ever. This Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) delves into the intricacies

¹ <https://health.ec.europa.eu/state-health-eu/health-glance-europe.en>

of the personalised prevention paradigm and elucidates the reasons for its crucial integration into European healthcare systems.

The personalised PREvention of Chronic Diseases (PRECeDI) consortium, established in 2019, laid the groundwork for the integration of personalised prevention into chronic disease.² It emphasized the potential of preventive interventions targeting high-risk individuals and underscored the need for parallel changes in healthcare systems, while highlighting the large gap between therapeutic offerings and prevention tools in the field of personalised medicine.

By leveraging these premises, the “*A personalised Prevention Roadmap for the Future Healthcare*” (PROPHET) project aims to bridge these gaps by advocating for a holistic approach that considers not only solid biomedical knowledge but also economic sustainability, policy alignment and investments in cutting-edge technologies. PROPHET is a Coordination and Support Action of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) and it involves 18 partners from 12 EU Member States, and the UK.

During the kickoff meeting of PROPHET in September 2022, personalised prevention was conceptualised as a targeted approach considering biological, environmental and behavioural characteristics, along with socio-economic and cultural context (“*personalised prevention aims to prevent onset, progression and recurrence of diseases through the adoption of targeted interventions that consider the biological information (e.g., genetic and other biomarkers, demographics, health conditions), environmental and behavioural characteristics, socio-economic and cultural context of individuals. This should be timely, effective and equitable in order to maintain the best possible balance in lifetime health trajectory*”).³ **As PROPHET is a Coordinating and Support Action of the International Consortium of Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed⁴), it emphasizes the integration of genomics/biomarkers in personalized preventive approaches.** Various terms, such as Precision Prevention or Precision (Public) Health⁵, are used interchangeably, emphasizing the need

² Boccia S, Pastorino R, Ricciardi W, Ádány R, Barnhoorn F, Boffetta P, Cornel MC, De Vito C, Gray M, Jani A, Lang M, Roldan J, Rosso A, Sánchez JM, Van Duijn CM, Van El CG, Villari P, Zawati MH. How to Integrate personalised Medicine into Prevention? Recommendations from the personalised Prevention of Chronic Diseases (PRECeDI) Consortium. Public Health Genomics. 2019;22(5-6):208-214. doi: 10.1159/000504652. Epub 2019 Dec 5. PMID: 31805565.

³ Concept paper on Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, available at <https://prophetproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/PROPHET-Concept-paper.pdf>

⁴ Home - ICPerMed

⁵ Roberts, M. C., Holt, K. E., Del Fiol, G., Baccarelli, A. A., & Allen, C. G. (2024). Precision public health in the era of genomics and big data. Nature Medicine, 1-9.

for precision and effectiveness in health promotion. The Fig. 2 depicts our vision of the three levels of personalised prevention in PROPHET.

Figure 2. Description of the three levels of prevention, according to the disease stage.

Initiatives like PRoCEDi and PROPHET chart a course towards the integration of personalised prevention into the fabric of European healthcare. The transition from reactive treatment models to proactive and individualised preventive measures holds the promise of a healthier and more sustainable future for all people across the continent. Embracing personalised prevention is not just a choice: it is a necessity for building resilient and effective healthcare systems that can withstand the complex health challenges of the 21st century.

2.2 PROPHET expected outcomes

The PROPHET project anticipates a spectrum of far-reaching outcomes and impactful contributions, strategically aligned with the overarching mission to innovate healthcare through the implementation of Personalised Prevention as an integral part of the current traditional approaches in prevention. PROPHET employs a structured methodology, including the creation of a Stakeholder Platform, literature mapping, research gap analysis and the development of the PROPHET Framework. The outputs are disseminated through targeted communication strategies and capacity-building activities to maximize the impact of Personalised Prevention strategies across various stakeholder groups. These expected outcomes encompass a multidimensional approach, addressing various domains and stakeholders, with a profound emphasis on sustainability, innovation and societal well-being.

Main expected outcomes are:

1. Comprehensive Personalised Prevention Roadmap
2. Strengthened Collaborative Ecosystem
3. In-Depth Research Advancements
4. Evaluative Frameworks and Indicators
5. Empowered Public Health Authorities
6. Raised Awareness among Citizens, Patients and Healthcare Professionals and Citizen Engagement
7. Informed policy makers thanks to Policy Briefs and Communication Strategies

A detailed description of expected outputs and outcomes is set out in Table 1.

In summary, the expected outcomes and impact of the PROPHET project extend beyond the development of a Roadmap; they encompass a holistic transformation of healthcare practices, stakeholder collaborations, research advancements and societal awareness.

The project's endeavors are poised to pave the way towards a future where personalised prevention is not just a concept but a tangible and integral component of healthcare excellence.

	Goal	Activities	Main Outputs	Expected Outcomes
Foster Collaboration, comprehensive personalised prevention Roadmap for effective prevention and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda	Establish a comprehensive personalised prevention Roadmap. Establish collaboration among stakeholders in the field of personalised Prevention for the creation and implementation of a SRIA.	Create a Stakeholder Platform, to engage key stakeholders in order to contribute to the SRIA on personalised Prevention, to inform research funders and prospective partners. Develop a detailed Roadmap outlining actions, output and results indicators.	A Stakeholder Platform, a structured mechanism for SRIA co-creation and a comprehensive SRIA translating PROPHET's vision into a long-term systemic approach.	<p>1. <u>Comprehensive personalised Prevention Roadmap</u></p> <p>This accompanies the SRIA and details the actions and timelines by which this SRIA is expected to be implemented. The Roadmap provides a detailed blueprint for implementing tailored preventive strategies for each individual, based on the latest scientific advancements and the specific needs of each context.</p> <p>2. <u>Strengthened Collaborative Ecosystem</u></p> <p>A relevant activity of PROPHET is to strengthen the collaboration network among all stakeholders involved in the field of personalised prevention, aiming to create a robust and sustainable ecosystem.</p>
Research Advancements in personalised Prevention	Gain a thorough understanding of research advancements in personalised Prevention through literature mapping, research gap analysis and mapping existing funded projects and programs.	Conduct literature mapping, research gap analysis and mapping of existing research projects and programs for personalised Prevention in Europe and beyond.	Mapping reports of the existing scientific literature in the domains of personalised Prevention.	<p>3. <u>In-Depth Research Advancements in personalised Prevention</u></p> <p>Literature mapping, research gap analysis and mapping of recent research projects and programs are expected to yield insightful reports in the domains of personalised Prevention. These outputs will not only inform the development of the personalised Prevention Roadmap but also contribute to the broader scientific community, advancing knowledge and guiding future research initiatives.</p>
Provide instruments to evaluate the Effectiveness and Clinical Utility of personalised	Assess the clinical utility, key success factors and gaps of current personalised preventive approaches. Identify	Conduct literature reviews on the evaluation frameworks used to appraise omics technologies and extract	Analysis of adoption of approaches in all domains, identification of facilitators / barriers and a list of indicators to	<p>4. <u>Evaluative Frameworks and Indicators</u></p> <p>A significant outcome of the project is the establishment of evaluative frameworks and indicators for personalised Prevention approaches. Through a meticulous analysis of existing bottlenecks, success factors and barriers, PROPHET will identify key process and</p>

<p>preventive approaches</p>	<p>bottlenecks, analyze evidence and evaluate successful implementations.</p>	<p>the indicators to evaluate the relevant domains of clinical utility.</p>	<p>evaluate personalised Prevention approaches.</p>	<p>outcome indicators. These indicators will serve as essential tools for assessing the clinical utility and scalability of personalised preventive approaches, providing a tangible contribution to evidence-based healthcare practices.</p>
<p>Strengthen Public Health Authorities</p>	<p>Analyze how personalised Prevention can be delivered most effectively, efficiently and cost-effectively. Design a multidimensional framework (the PROPHET Framework) for appraising and adopting personalised preventive approaches.</p>	<p>Develop the PROPHET Framework and apply it to assess existing personalised prevention programs. Provide Capacity Building activities for Policy Makers and Health professionals through dedicated tool boxes and residential and educational efforts</p>	<p>The PROPHET Framework, 3 case studies and 4 Action Plans for personalised Prevention programs and Capacity Building activities.</p>	<p>5. Empowered Public Health Authorities The project aims to empower Public Health Authorities by providing them with a multidimensional framework for designing, assessing and implementing personalised preventive approaches. This framework, integrated into the SRIA, is expected to be a practical resource for policymakers and health authorities, enhancing their capacity to navigate the complexities of personalised Prevention and make informed decisions that benefit public health.</p>
<p>Raise Awareness among Citizens and Patients</p>	<p>Raise awareness among public and patients on the potential of personalised Prevention to improve quality of life. Engage them in defining, establishing and adopting personalised preventive services.</p>	<p>Implement awareness campaigns, capacity building for public and patients and develop tailored communication tools.</p>	<p>Guidelines for public and patient engagement, policy briefs and communication strategies tailored to stakeholders. Delivery of training courses, targeted awareness campaigns and capacity-building activities.</p>	<p>6. Raised Awareness among Public, Patients and Healthcare Professionals and Patient Engagement The project aims to empower individuals to actively engage in their health journey. This outcome extends to a broader cultural shift, where a patient-centric approach is encouraged, fostering open dialogues between health professionals, patients and their families.</p>

Raise Awareness among Healthcare Professionals and Stakeholders	Raise awareness among Health Professionals, Life Sciences Companies, Insurers, Regulators and Policy Makers. Promote collaborative relationships for the quick adoption of personalised Prevention approaches.	Stakeholder involvement via the Stakeholder Platform, awareness campaigns and capacity building for healthcare professionals.	Guidelines for stakeholder engagement, policy briefs and communication strategies tailored to targeted stakeholders.	<u>Raised Awareness of healthcare professionals and policy makers</u> Through the elaboration of a policy brief and tailored communication strategies, PROPHET aims to influence decision-makers, ensuring that the insights and recommendations derived from the project are disseminated effectively. This outreach is designed to catalyze policy changes that align with the vision of integrating personalised Prevention into the fabric of healthcare systems.
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Table 1. PROPHET Goals, activities, main outputs and expected outcomes.

2.3 Building on lessons learned

One of the fundamental theoretical underpinnings of PROPHET is the “Vision Paper on Personalised Medicine Research & Implementation by 2030” by ICPeMed, a comprehensive and forward-thinking approach that envisions the integration of personalised prevention strategies as a fundamental element in the evolution of healthcare for all the public⁶. This vision is based on the idea that tailoring medical interventions to individual characteristics, including genetic, environmental and lifestyle factors, holds the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of healthcare delivery⁷).⁸ ICPeMed was created in 2015, bringing together over 50 European and international partners, working as a “think tank” focused on Policy and Strategy for Personalised medicine and on fostering Internationalization and Global cooperation. Over the past 10 years, ICPeMed produced several key documents to foster research and implementation in Personalised medicine, including an Action Plan (<https://www.icpermed.eu/activities/action-plan/>; 2017) and a ICPeMed's Vision 2030 reflects a concerted effort to engage a wide array of stakeholders, including experts from diverse professional backgrounds and sectors, to ensure that the implementation of personalised medicine is both inclusive and impactful. The emphasis on personalised prevention approaches within this vision aligns with the broader goal of empowering individuals to actively participate in maintaining their health and well-being. By integrating personalised prevention into the fabric of healthcare, ICPeMed envisions a future where individuals are equipped with the knowledge and tools to make informed decisions about their health, thereby contributing to improved health outcomes on a societal level. Furthermore, the ICPeMed's vision emphasizes the need for a paradigm shift in healthcare systems to accommodate the principles of personalised medicine. This includes fostering an environment that supports the responsible use of health-related data. By placing personalised prevention at the forefront of its vision, ICPeMed acknowledges the potential of these strategies to not only improve individual health but also to contribute to the sustainability and resilience of healthcare systems as a whole.⁹

⁶ <https://www.icpermed.eu/en/activities-vision-paper.php>

⁷ <https://translational-medicine.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12967-020-02316-w>

⁸ <https://www.eppermed.eu>

⁹ Aguilera-Cobos L, García-Sanz P, Rosario-Lozano MP, Claros MG, Blasco-Amaro JA. An innovative framework to determine the implementation level of personalised medicine: A systematic review. *Front Public Health*. 2023 Feb 3;11:1039688. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1039688. PMID: 36817923; PMCID: PMC9936069.

2.3.1 Promising stories in personalised prevention

In the countries where top level scientific expertise and universal countrywide coverage of health insurance and medical services are supported by forward-looking and timely established legislation, inspiring examples have been set as outgrowths of public-private partnership. To illustrate a real-life application in a well-studied area¹⁰, personalised prevention in breast cancer includes tailoring screening recommendations to individual risk, initiating earlier surveillance based on Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS), offering additional genetic testing for high-risk variants when needed, and ensuring access to qualified medical support. These steps represent the foundation of personalised prevention and care in a field where delays can cost lives. Additionally, targeted analysis of specific patient pathways from prevention and pre-diagnosis to recovery or end-of-life care brings together key stakeholders from various sectors and effectively identifies key development needs, which can then be prioritized based on their importance and feasibility¹¹.

Making a change in paradigm takes time – however, this statement should not postpone the first steps to be taken as soon as possible. As an essential prerequisite to build a solid basis for a country-wide personalised medicine system, the medical and related data management must meet the highest level security standards, yet perform fluently. In Estonia, this is called the e-Health system. Its main success factors are clear governance, legal clarity, a mature ecosystem, agreement about access rights, and standardization of medical data and data exchange rules¹². Consequently, more than 20 years of a general population biobank (EstBB, part of BBMRI-ERIC network of biobanks) have created transversal competences in science, medical practices and healthcare governance both locally and internationally. The experience from several pilot projects carried out using the wide spectrum of the scientific capacities of EstBB^{13, 14} now serve as examples of how far the best outputs from a biobank can reach to, and accelerate the medical practices in Estonia and elsewhere.

¹⁰ Padrik P, Puustusmaa M, Tõnisson N, et al. Implementation of Risk-Stratified Breast Cancer Prevention With a Polygenic Risk Score Test in Clinical Practice. *Breast Cancer: Basic and Clinical Research*. 2023;17. doi:10.1177/11782234231205700

¹¹ <https://www.sm.ee/en/news/lung-cancer-patient-pathway-project-illuminates-gaps-cancer-care>

¹² Klementi T, Piho G, Ross P. A reference architecture for personal health data spaces using decentralized content-addressable storage networks. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2024 Jul 16;11:1411013. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2024.1411013. PMID: 39081693; PMCID: PMC11286498.

¹³ Alver M, Palover M, Saar A, Läll K, Zekavat SM, Tõnisson N, Leitsalu L, Reigo A, Nikopensius T, Ainla T, Kals M, Mägi R, Gabriel SB, Eha J, Lander ES, Irs A, Philippakis A, Marandi T, Natarajan P, Metspalu A, Kathiresan S, Esko T. Recall by genotype and cascade screening for familial hypercholesterolemia in a population-based biobank from Estonia. *Genet Med*. 2019 May;21(5):1173-1180. doi: 10.1038/s41436-018-0311-2. Epub 2018 Oct 1. PMID: 30270359; PMCID: PMC6443485.

¹⁴ Leitsalu L, Palover M, Sikka TT, Reigo A, Kals M, Pärn K, Nikopensius T, Esko T, Metspalu A, Padrik P, Tõnisson N. Genotype-first approach to the detection of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer risk, and effects of risk disclosure to biobank participants. *Eur J Hum Genet*. 2021 Mar;29(3):471-481. doi: 10.1038/s41431-020-00760-2. Epub 2020 Nov 23. PMID: 33230308; PMCID: PMC7940387.

Biobanks in several countries have started to return results of findings with implications for care and prevention. Pilots have been done and are ongoing on how best to deliver such information. For instance, participants can be contacted by the biobank or access their results via a portal.¹⁵ Lessons from the Estonian biobank include participant reactions to such results and ways to deliver these results via counselling, which may prove to be time consuming.¹⁶

In Finland, participants can access their own 10-year absolute risk estimate for Type 2 Diabetes, which combines traditional risk factors (such as BMI and cholesterol levels) with Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS). Participants can compare their own total risk with a matched age population, their projected risk at age 60, and calculate changes to their risk if they would make lifestyle changes, such as stopping smoking. Such tools may help participants understand their own role in improving their health and promote citizen empowerment.

The P5.fi Study, based on Finland's FinHealth 2017 population-based study, assessed how individuals responded to personalized genetic risk information and its influence on health behaviors. Focusing on polygenic risk scores for coronary artery disease, type 2 diabetes, and deep vein thrombosis risks, it provided biobank donors with secure, personalized reports of the genetic and total risk for these diseases. Relevant pharmacogenetic and single variants for the diseases were likewise analyzed and the results returned. The study provided lifestyle guidance and information about the diseases and genetics through the MyP5 website. Participants' responses and health outcomes were monitored over years to evaluate the feasibility of integrating genomic data into public health, aiming to address challenges in applying predictive, preventive, and personalized health approaches.^{17, 18}

The GenomeHealth project, a collaboration between Finnish hospital biobanks, aims to integrate genomic data from biobank samples into healthcare to advance personalized medicine. The study utilizes the genomic data created by the Finngen-study¹⁹. By screening high-risk genes like *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2* for cancer susceptibility, the project developed a streamlined process for delivering significant genetic findings to biobank donors. The variants selected to be screened in the project are well-known, and there are clear action models and treatment recommendations for them,

¹⁵ Estonian Biobank Launches Portal to Deliver Genetic Results to Biobank Participants - Research In Estonia. Frontiers | A Web Portal for Communicating Polygenic Risk Score Results for Health Care Use—The P5 Study (frontiersin.org).

¹⁶ Lessons learned during the process of reporting individual genomic results to participants of a population-based biobank - PubMed (nih.gov)

¹⁷ <https://thl.fi/en/research-and-development/research-and-projects/the-p5.fi-study-genetic-information-for-health-support>

¹⁸ Ref: Marjonen H, Marttila M, Paajanen T, Vornanen M, Brunfeldt M, Joensuu A, Halmesvaara O, Aro K, Alanne-Kinnunen M, Jousilahti P, Borodulin K, Koskinen S, Tuomi T, Ilanne-Parikka P, Lindström J, Laine MK, Auro K, Kääriäinen H, Perola M, Kristiansson K. A Web Portal for Communicating Polygenic Risk Score Results for Health Care Use-The P5 Study. *Front Genet.* 2021 Oct 29;12:763159. doi: 10.3389/fgene.2021.763159. PMID: 34777479; PMCID: PMC8585790.

¹⁹ www.finngen.fi

including enhanced follow-up, preventive surgery, and targeted therapy such as PARP inhibitors. Utilizing the MyBiobank digital service, donors were contacted and, with consent, informed of their genetic risks, then referred to clinical services for further testing and counseling. This approach not only supports early disease intervention but also demonstrates cost-effectiveness, highlighting Finnish biobanks' potential in preventive healthcare. Also cost-benefit analyses of the approach are being done.²⁰

The vast majority of both the studies participants were satisfied with the provided services.

On top of health benefits, these studies as well as previous research showed that analyses of biobank samples can be done very cost-effectively, and in some cases, even saving costs.²¹

2.4 Synergies with other initiatives

During the different stages of project development, PROPHET will make contact and synergies with numerous initiatives.

First, PROPHET is fully matched and aligned in purpose with the Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, reflecting a resolute political commitment to comprehensively combat cancer. The plan is structured around key action areas and provides a holistic approach, addressing the entire spectrum of the disease pathway, from prevention to treatment and emphasizing the improvement of the quality of life for cancer patients and survivors. PROPHET's activities are intricately aligned with the nuanced Roadmap of action 31.2, the “Roadmap to personalised Prevention”, making a substantive contribution to the overarching goals of the Europe's Beating Cancer Plan.²²

The project supports personalised prevention within the cancer, that can serve as blueprint for successful initiatives in other chronic diseases, and extends its influence on pivotal European initiatives, notably collaborating with ICPeMed and the European Partnership for Personalised Medicine (EP PerMed was launched on October 5, 2023, marking a significant milestone in advancing research in personalised medicine across Europe., EP PerMed rallied 60 partners to contribute to its development, with the primary goal of advancing innovative personalised medicine approaches in

²⁰ <https://site.fingenious.fi/en/articles/genomehealth-project-returns-genetic-results>

²¹ Martikainen J, Lehtimäki AV, Jalkanen K, Lavikainen P, Paajanen T, Marjonen H, Kristiansson K, Lindström J, Perola M. Economic evaluation of using polygenic risk score to guide risk screening and interventions for the prevention of type 2 diabetes in individuals with high overall baseline risk. *Front Genet.* 2022 Sep 15;13:880799. doi: 10.3389/fgene.2022.880799. PMID: 36186460; PMCID: PMC95202

²² https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/2021-2025_cancer-roadmap1_en_0.pdf

healthcare systems. EP PerMed's initiatives are underpinned by the SRIA for personalised medicine published in 2023²³, another key document useful in the construction of PROPHET's SRIA. This collaborative synergy enriches the landscape of personalised medicine, contributing significantly to the realization of a fortified European Health Union characterized by resilience, preparedness and sustainability in the face of evolving health challenges.

The concept of personalised prevention inevitably relies on the availability of data that allows for the individualization of healthcare interventions, as well as the creation of infrastructures that enable data sharing in a manner compliant with high European standards for both the effectiveness of healthcare systems and the protection of citizens' and patients' privacy and data security. To address these needs, the European Commission has funded three initiatives/projects: in 2018, the *1+Million Genomes (1+MG)*²⁴ initiative was launched. Twenty-six European countries have signed the declaration, aiming to enable secure access to genomic and corresponding clinical data across Europe for better research, personalised healthcare, and health policy making. In 2020, the *Beyond 1 Million Genomes (BIMG)*²⁵ project was initiated, focusing on the goals of the design and testing phase of the 1+MG Initiative. BIMG produced the 1+MG Framework²⁶ a user-friendly interface to navigate the guidelines and recommendations of the 1+MG initiative. As results of a common effort of 1+MG and B1+MG, the **1+MG Roadmap 2023-2027** has been published.²⁷

Subsequently, in 2022, the *Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)*²⁸ project began. This €40M co-funded project builds on the preparatory work of the 1+MG working groups, the BIMG project, and investments from EU countries. The GDI project is enabling access to genomic and related phenotypic and clinical data across Europe by establishing a federated, sustainable, and secure infrastructure for data access. Both projects are coordinated by ELIXIR, which acts as a neutral broker for the 1+MG countries and aims to sustain biological infrastructure to support the initiative's ambitions. The *Genome of Europe* project also supports the 1+MG initiative and started in October 2024. The project is building a European network of national genomic reference cohorts of 1,000,000 citizens, selected to be representative of the European population. It is worth mentioning in this context the latest report from the WHO²⁹ that, by recognizing the importance and value of human genome data, provides

²³ The EP PerMed: 'The Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for Personalised Medicine' (2023)

²⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

²⁵ <https://b1mg-project.eu>

²⁶ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/about-the-framework>

²⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/99974>

²⁸ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu>

²⁹ Guidance for human genome data collection, access, use and sharing: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240102149>

guidance to realize the promise of genomics for all in a way that identifies and mitigates the ethical, legal, social and cultural issues that are likely to arise.

Lastly the *Transforming Health and Care Systems* (THCS) European Partnership, co-financed by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Framework, stands as a noteworthy initiative supporting personalised prevention advocated by PROPHET. By backing coordinated national and regional research, innovation programs, capacity development and networking, THCS actively contributes to the transformation of healthcare and care systems across Europe. In facing common challenges, healthcare and care systems in Europe necessitate harmonised solutions and THCS serves as a strategic opportunity to unite stakeholders and facilitate the digital transformation of healthcare services. With a goal to transition towards more sustainable, efficient, resilient, inclusive, innovative and high-quality healthcare and care systems, THCS aims to generate new knowledge, co-design solutions and strengthen healthcare systems through diverse activities.

The collective commitment of PROPHET and other initiatives enriches the landscape of personalised medicine, paving the way for a future where individualised healthcare becomes a cornerstone of the European healthcare system.

In conclusion, the integration of the results from different projects and initiatives is crucial to implement personalised prevention at European level and beyond.

2.5 Mission: the need of a SRIA on personalised prevention

The current document aims to support EU Member States when scaling up personalised preventive approaches for primary, secondary and tertiary prevention, interweaving the levels of biomarkers, individual behavior, and environment/societal factors. Unlike the traditional *one-size-fits-all* approach, which applies the same preventive measures to everyone, personalised prevention focuses on tailored interventions based on individual health profiles and risk factors. By considering the outcomes listed in Table 1, this SRIA seeks to address the key elements required to ensure that personalised prevention strategies are effectively implemented and that their benefits are realized across Europe.

2.6 Methodology for SRIA development

The SRIA is grounded in a highly multidisciplinary construction model, integrating the consortium's vision for personalised prevention (summarised in a Concept Paper described in 2.6.1), and the

assessment and synthesis of various project outcomes through a co-creation process ensured by robust stakeholder engagement. In terms of evidence, the SRIA draws from all three major phases (and related Work Packages-WP) constituting the PROPHET approach: **Mapping**, which involves extensive research on the state of personalised prevention in Europe and beyond; the **Assessment** process, built around the PROPHET Framework, that provides decision-makers with a path and related indicators to evaluate personalised prevention approaches before implementation; the **Building** phase that presents results from the actual implementation of the PROPHET methodology in diverse health and social contexts. The stepwise approach for SRIA development is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The approach for SRIA development in PROPHET.

2.6.1 The PROPHET Concept Paper

Efforts from the first year of activities of PROPHET have been summarized in a Concept Paper³⁰, which served as the foundation for the full Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) in the field of personalised prevention. This document encapsulates the consortium's vision, definition, and initial insights regarding the gaps and challenges of personalised prevention that need to be analyzed

³⁰ Concept paper on Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, available at <https://prophetproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/PROPHET-Concept-paper.pdf>

for its implementation. The Concept Paper has been informed by preliminary results of literature reviews, mapping analyses, and input from a wide range of stakeholder and key informant interviews and consultations at European and national levels.

The paper defines personalised prevention and its links with previous European initiatives in personalised medicine. It highlights PROPHET's role and the SRIA as a tool to support the implementation of innovative, sustainable, and effective personalised programs to prevent common chronic diseases in all European Member States. Precision in interventions implies predicting and addressing risk (at scale), in individuals as well as groups of individuals sharing different characteristics. Here the high-risk vs the population (subgroup) approach needs to be balanced recognizing Rose's prevention paradox³¹. In essence, effective public health prevention must strike a careful balance between precision targeting for high-risk groups and broader measures for the general population. This trade off depends on how much risk is confined to an identifiable population group, and the extent to which precision can be achieved in identifying this group and addressing this increased risk. This is likely to vary across risk factors and diseases, and across socioeconomic groups and whether these groups have access to health and social services.

The project's strategy involves engaging the broad health ecosystem and addressing individual risks within a community context, especially for primary prevention in healthy individuals (Fig.4). Data plays a central role in this approach, categorized into three subsections in PROPHET: biomarker, individual lifestyles and environmental/contextual factors. The disease and life-course stages, ranging from healthy to sick, involve actions across promotion/primary prevention, secondary prevention and tertiary prevention/treatment level.

³¹ Rose, Geoffrey, Kay-Tee Khaw, and Michael Marmot, *Rose's Strategy of Preventive Medicine* (Oxford, 2008; online edn, Oxford Academic, 1 Sept. 2009), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780192630971.001.0001>, accessed 26 Feb. 2024.

Figure 4. Potential source of information needed to achieve precision and personalization of prevention and treatment across the life course.

The Concept Paper also preliminarily identified preliminary challenges that constitute the core of the PROPHET project:

- The data challenge: practical and legal impediments currently hinder the potential to use and combine different types of data in prevention, which need to be addressed to increase precision in the identification of individuals, families, population groups, or neighborhoods at increased risk, combined with individual empowerment and health literacy.
- Trust, ethics, and community engagement: public health actions should focus on population-specific needs, policy development, and delivering effective and ethical interventions. Crucial activities include engaging communities, sharing data, building coalitions, improving health literacy, and developing a diverse educated workforce. A fundamental concern is whether precision technologies can exacerbate health disparities or create barriers to access for certain populations. Ethical principles of justice, fairness and equity in access will therefore need to guide assessment of precision technologies, in addition to various health technology assessments.

- Behavioral Science: personalised prevention assesses risk, which needs to be managed by the person exposed and stakeholders, including health workers, who can affect risk behavior and exposure. This suggests a behavioral science research agenda to develop an evidence-based approach to tackling risk.
- Health Sector integration and beyond: as personalised prevention interventions develop, they need to be integrated into health services, raising questions about health worker capabilities, systems support, financing/reimbursement, and incentive mechanisms to support prevention interventions.
- Technological advances add new markers that may help better identify subgroups of individuals with different risks of having a disease, which eventually could improve prevention strategies at the individual level. Integrating markers of risk into scalable intervention packages is key to achieve population impact.
- Political economy of prevention: what gets recognized, becomes policy and implemented, is not just a question of the evidence at hand, but also of the political economy, a social science conceptualisation of what gets done or not. During PROPHET stakeholder consultation it became evident that a stakeholder forum for multisectoral coordination and advocacy was desirable, at regional as well as national level. Such a forum could work on the narrative and positioning for prevention, and approach policymakers and stakeholders across sectors.
- Inequities in health and personalised prevention: Inequities in health outcomes are driven by differential risk mostly linked to biological and socio-economic factors. Measures across promotion, prevention, and treatment need to be adapted and highly contextualized to improve health.
- Scaling up- Implementation Research: As interventions are put into practice in complex health systems, issues around implementation and operational questions need to be addressed.

In summary, to realize its potential the precision field needs to take a life course, multisectoral approach using different types of data also to prevent disease and not restrict itself to using omic information to treat established disease. This implies a far-reaching research and innovation need, new governance mechanisms, and a balanced agenda assessing both individual utility and public health implications at population level.

2.6.2 Stakeholder engagement strategy

This specific activity will be completed and validated within the project lifespan. The stakeholder engagement strategy is implemented through the PROPHET Platform and the PROPHET Forum. One of the foundational elements of the PROPHET project, and subsequently the development of the SRIA, is the continuous engagement of stakeholders in the realm of personalised prevention, following a process defined as co-creation. This collaborative approach aims to bring together researchers, policymakers, healthcare professionals, patient and citizen representatives and other key stakeholders to drive advancements in the field. To achieve this, a thorough stakeholder mapping exercise, based on the “snowball methodology”, was conducted to identify and categorise relevant stakeholders across Europe. This process started by identifying key stakeholders, suggested by partners, then extending the process to other stakeholders who might have an interest in the project. A (confidential) database of contacts was then established, which is continuously updated with new data, ensuring a thorough follow-up and involvement of stakeholders from all relevant groups. Access to this database is limited to PROPHET project partners.

The stakeholder engagement strategy outlines the approach to engage experts from various sectors, ensuring that the potential stakeholders' concerns and needs are considered in the development of the SRIA (Table 2).

Diverse channels and tools have been used to reach stakeholders, informing them about project activities and results, and encouraging their active participation in knowledge sharing activities such as workshops. At the heart of this engagement process is **the PROPHET Forum**, a stakeholder community that gathers stakeholders from all relevant categories. The Forum is managed and coordinated by the PROPHET project team, **with regular outreach to stakeholders to engage them in project events and ask them to contribute to the SRIA co-development process**. To facilitate exchanges and interactions among Forum members, the **PROPHET Platform** was developed as a **community platform**. The Platform offers members the ability to set up individual profiles, use features such as unity web platform bilateral exchange through a matchmaking tool, share information with peers and with the PROPHET team, access event information and recordings, and engage with co-developed documents, including the SRIA and related documents. This coordinated approach, supported by the PROPHET Forum and Platform, aims to maintain a stakeholder engagement process that is crucial for the success of the PROPHET project and the development of the SRIA.

Stakeholders	Concerns	Potential impacts
Patients & citizens	They are the most important key stakeholders as they are the ultimate beneficiaries of more targeted prevention and treatments. They may be concerned about the cost of personalised preventive treatments, access to genetic testing, etc.	Improved patients' and citizens' quality of life by adapting prevention to individual characteristics (including genomics and environment / lifestyle aspects).
Healthcare professionals	Concerns about the cost and feasibility of implementing personalised preventive approaches in health systems as well as the training and education on these new approaches.	Informed and trained professionals, emphasising prevention over treatment; early detection of potential risks among their patients and thus early approach to treatment where necessary; less overload in hospitals thanks to prevention and early treatment.
Researchers	Funding of research and collaboration with other stakeholders to advance in personalised prevention research.	New collaboration opportunities through research programmes to advance in the field of personalised prevention.
Policy makers & public authorities	Need to make new regulations or improve the existing ones as well as ensuring the safety and effectiveness of personalised preventive approaches and treatments. Validity of approaches across the EU and transferability of results.	Reduced burden on the health and social security systems thanks to prevention and early treatment, reducing costs. EU-wide approach and transferability tested through dedicated use cases which are nurturing the SRIA.
Insurers	Reimbursement processes of personalised preventive approaches.	Demonstrate the cost effectiveness & value of personalised prevention approaches, alleviating the burden on insurers.
Life Science Companies	Regulatory barriers for developing personalised prevention approaches and long processes.	Provide guidelines for the development of future personalised prevention approaches and "citizens" engagement.

Table 2. Anticipated key stakeholders concerns and potential impacts to be addressed in the development of the SRIA.

2.6.3 The Consultation Process for the Development of the SRIA

The development of the SRIA has followed a structured, multi-phase process since the early stages of the PROPHET project, combining conceptual elaboration, expert input, and progressive validation through stakeholder and public engagement.

The process began in August 2023 with the release of the Concept Paper (presented in detail in paragraph 2.6.1), which laid out the preliminary vision for personalised prevention and introduced a conceptual model for integrated, multilevel precision prevention. This document served as the foundation for subsequent development.

In September 2024, the first version of the SRIA was completed. It expanded on the conceptual model introduced in the Concept Paper and incorporated key findings from the mapping activities conducted in the project, as well as the main challenges to be addressed in the coming years. These challenges span multiple dimensions: from broadening the understanding and scope of promotion and prevention strategies, to establishing continuous systems for evidence synthesis that support personalised approaches. They also include defining practical pathways for implementing the PROPHET framework (Fig. 5), ensuring robust mechanisms for data collection and integration, and building the necessary data infrastructure.

Figure 5. Overall PROPHET framework for genetic testing, including HTA complemented by HIA and a monitoring phase.

Furthermore, the process emphasised the importance of fostering trust and engagement within communities, ensuring the active involvement of health professionals and policymakers, and addressing regulatory issues while promoting synergies with the private sector. Equally crucial are efforts to guarantee equitable access and coverage, manage ethical, legal, and social implications, and develop strategies to support behavioural change among individuals and populations.

All these priorities were identified and selected through extensive internal discussion among stakeholders, ensuring that the SRIA reflects a shared vision and consensus within the PROPHET community.

To further refine the document, a dedicated workshop was organised in Stockholm in October 2024, where the first version of the SRIA was presented and discussed with stakeholders. In preparation for the consultation phase, a specific workshop on pharmacogenomics was held in Amsterdam in January 2025, bringing together experts and stakeholders to explore challenges and opportunities in one of the SRIA's key thematic areas.

Building on the insights gathered, an updated version of the SRIA was prepared, together with the drafting of a first version of the Roadmap, between October 2024 and March 2025. The Roadmap was designed to translate the strategic priorities outlined in the SRIA into actionable directions and milestones.

A subsequent phase of targeted stakeholder consultation was carried out between April and May 2025 to gather further input on the updated versions of both the SRIA and the Roadmap. Feedback from a broad set of stakeholders helped validate the priorities and refine the implementation framework. Following this, a public consultation was launched to reach a wider audience across Europe. This phase provided additional insights from citizens, practitioners, researchers, and organisations who had not been previously engaged.

All these contributions are being integrated into the final version of the SRIA, which includes the Roadmap as an embedded component. While the SRIA outlines ten key challenges and corresponding priorities, described in detail later in this document (Section 3), spanning scientific, ethical, societal, organisational, and policy dimensions, the Roadmap complements it with an actionable implementation pathway. It identifies concrete steps, responsible actors, timelines, and enabling

conditions needed to translate strategic priorities into effective interventions at both national and EU levels.

The final SRIA, to be published by November 2025, can represent a consolidated and shared vision for advancing personalised prevention in Europe.

3. The challenges of personalised prevention

Challenge 1: The broad scope of promotion and prevention

Status

Over the years, research on the prevention of chronic diseases has generated a substantial body of evidence. Effective strategies to reduce the risk of developing chronic diseases include lifestyle changes—such as healthy diets, exercise, sleep or smoking cessation-, reduction of occupational hazards and environmental exposures (e.g. air pollution or chemical contaminants), as well as primary care or public health preventive programs (e.g. screening, vaccination, metabolic risk factors control).³² These strategies can also be promoted or implemented through multilevel legal, societal, and public health measures that often extend beyond the health sector. The ambition, and potential, of a “precision dividend” is to reduce poor health and premature mortality by up to 70%. In this broader context, personalized prevention aims to advance efforts by incorporating the new possibilities offered by technological advancements in both biological and data science. A recent paper by Bian (2024) focused on lifespan, estimated that, while unfavorable lifestyles increased risk of death by 78%, those with an unfavorable genetic predisposition also had a 21% increased risk of death compared with a low genetic risk independent of lifestyle factor (Bian, 2024). However, today, technological advancements provide new opportunities to explore the drivers of illness and mortality. A recent study by Artengieri (2025) exemplifies this progress, utilizing exposome-wide association analyses in the UK Biobank cohort to assess the relative contributions of genetic susceptibility (polygenic risk scores) and environmental factors (the exposome). The study also incorporated -omic-derived biomarkers to examine proteomic aging and mortality. Findings revealed that, compared to basic demographic information like age and sex, polygenic risk scores for 22 major diseases accounted for less than a 2% increase in explained mortality variation, whereas the exposome

³² Prüss-Üstün A, Corvalán C. Preventing disease through healthy environments: an estimate of the environmental burden of disease. Geneva: WHO; 2006.

contributed an additional 17%. In fact, an individual's risk of developing any disease is shaped by the interplay of sociocultural, economic, and physical environments (e.g. education level, income, housing and employment conditions, cultural patterns and legal context, family and social networks, pollution and climate change). These factors influence lifestyles and behaviors (e.g. dietary pattern, physical activity, tobacco or other substances use) that, combined with environmental exposures, genetic predispositions, and biological elements, determine disease susceptibility. While considerable research examines these factors independently, studies exploring their interactions are limited. Understanding these relationships is crucial for improving prediction accuracy and refining personalized preventive strategies. Since this SRIA primarily focuses on the omics sciences sector, a priority challenge for research should be to identify when these new resources provide real added value for prevention and how to integrate them effectively with existing knowledge and practical implementation strategies, without forgetting this global picture.

When it comes to omics, biomarkers are essential tools for identifying individuals at varying disease risk levels, whether in the general population or high-risk groups. They can function independently, be incorporated into predictive models, or work alongside digital tools like wearables and artificial intelligence for real-time monitoring. Traditional biomarkers, like blood pressure, blood sugar, and age, have guided prevention and treatment for decades. Now, advances in omics technologies—genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, microbiomics—provide additional data layers that enable finer risk stratification and tailored interventions. Furthermore, they can help estimate and refine risk exposures (e.g. exposomics). Molecular biomarkers, particularly genetic and genomic markers, dominate research in personalised primary and secondary prevention. However, genetic factors contribute moderately to disease origins and are less actionable compared to modifiable environmental and behavioral factors. Therefore, in addition to estimate the genetic risk of diseases, investigating gene-environment interactions is vital to understanding how genetic predispositions interact with external exposures and behaviors. This might expand the scope of the use of genetic data in prevention and pave the way for more personalised interventions. Emerging fields such as epigenetics and microbiomics also provide insights into modifiable risk factors. Epigenetic mechanisms, like DNA methylation, reflect how environmental exposures influence gene expression, linking modifiable factors like diet or stress to disease risk. Similarly, the microbiome -shaped by lifestyle and environmental influences- plays a relevant role in immune regulation, metabolism, and inflammation. Both epigenetics and microbiomics, as well as exposomics, may uncover actionable

pathways for tailoring interventions based on individual and environmental contexts. Additionally, expanding the use of other -omic technologies like transcriptomics and metabolomics may provide new opportunities for improving preventive strategies. Beyond molecular biomarkers, other tools, such as imaging biomarkers can offer insights into disease-related structural and functional variations, while anthropometric and physiological biomarkers may also enhance diagnostic accuracy in complex predictive models. Given the multimodal type of data that can predict risk, as well as adherence to and effectiveness of interventions, increasingly we will need to rely on algorithms and artificial intelligence to integrate data sources, which also need to prove their added value. This is an important area for research and innovation.

Gaps

The true potential of personalized prevention in public health can only be realized by incorporating both personal and contextual factors, including socioeconomic, environmental, and commercial determinants of health. Insights from these -omic strategies should enhance and complement this approach. However, our scoping review indicates that most biomarker research fails to consider these aspects. This is likely due to two key gaps: first, the lack of integration between non-clinical information and clinical or biological data, making their combination challenging; and second, the differing professional expertise required to interpret and manage each type of data. An integrative approach to personalized prevention should address these challenges.

Also, if personalised prevention strategies are primarily based on medical strategies delivered through health care, there is a risk of neglecting the social determinants of health. Omics-technologies applied through health services alone will achieve a smaller impact, particularly since vulnerable and high-risk individuals and groups tend to have less access and utilization of health services. However, data obtained from this integrative approach can also benefit and inform policies designed to address the broader factors mentioned above, and help them to achieve desired population impact, identifying high risk groups and promoting coverage.

It is the combined efforts of scientific advancements, including omics, as well as targeting social factors, and increased resource allocation that will be required for personalised prevention strategies to reduce disease burden and improve population health towards the ambition of preventing up to

70% of non-communicable diseases (NCDs). However, modelling and health economics research on incremental cost and health outcomes of -omics technologies in prevention beyond environmental/socioeconomic/lifestyle interventions would be useful. Also, the implementation part of the research and innovation agenda involves many sectors, and relies on several disciplinary areas, including political science. Nevertheless, these two issues are addressed in other challenges of this SRIA.

Among biomarkers, most current research focuses on identifying, quantifying and improving the estimation of genetic risk of diseases; however, while these efforts are particularly beneficial for individuals with inherited high-risk mutations, at the population level, polygenic risk scores currently have limited precision for individual risk prediction. While they may improve secondary prevention strategies, they are unlikely to serve as an effective guide for primary prevention. In contrast, the interaction between non-genetic risk factors and genes—a critical driver of disease development—as well as the role of other omics that might also incorporate environmental exposures remains underexplored, despite its potential to refine and focus personalised primary prevention strategies.

Another important gap in this field is the issue of external validity. In many cases, biomarker research is highly context-specific, making it unclear how results can be extrapolated to the general population. There is a need for large, consistent, and reliable population-based data. While significant efforts have been made at the European level in genomics, such as the Genome of Europe initiative, non-genetic data in these projects remain scarce. Several national initiatives within Europe have established large population-based cohorts that include genetic, epidemiological, clinical, and contextual data. Providing structural support for these initiatives, while promoting their integration and combined analyses, can enhance their impact on personalized prevention research. Studying the complex field of chronic disease prevention requires robust cohort data to generate meaningful insights.

Finally, governments and healthcare systems often face tough choices about how to allocate limited resources. In the research field, while there is significant funding for clinical trials related to drugs and diagnostics, there is far less investment in lifestyle interventions and prevention research, with or without omics involved. Similarly, for service delivery health budgets across European countries

typically spend 94% on care, and 6% on prevention. The imbalance between funding for clinical treatments and preventive strategies needs to be addressed, as greater attention to prevention could reduce the overall burden of disease and healthcare costs. A shift in funding priorities towards more preventive measures, to implement and scale preventive strategies, is needed for a more balanced and effective health system. This also implies the need for similar shifts in research and innovation.

Priorities and implementation

While this SRIA focuses mainly on genomics and its utility in a health systems context, there is need to address the multisectoral, and multilevel components to realize the potential of personalised prevention. This integrative approach will need to include also governance, and systems change of the physical-, food- and social- environments where citizens lead their lives. This will require also e.g. research and innovation agendas in political- and systems- science. But it also requires data and data integration. Many relevant sources of non-clinical information from different sectors (e.g., socioeconomic, environmental, and contextual) should inform personalized prevention, and omics research must incorporate them. The key challenges lie in making this information accessible and ensuring its compatibility with other data sources. Another priority should be the seamless integration of these diverse data types to enhance the effectiveness of personalized prevention strategies.

Also, prioritizing research into biomarkers that reflect modifiable factors is essential. Greater emphasis should be placed on improving methods for measuring relevant exposures, in studying gene-environment interactions and in understanding and incorporating omics that can help to understand the environmental origin of diseases, to develop personalised primary prevention. Context must also be incorporated as a key modulating factor. In addition, incorporating technologies like wearables and leveraging artificial intelligence will also be vital for interpreting and utilizing the data generated by omics studies.

Strengthening and combining existing large European population-based cohorts -which include genetic and clinical information, as well as rich epidemiological, contextual, and exposure data, and often have associated biobanks—may be an efficient way to conduct studies in this field. Supporting them and promoting the use of their data within the research community may be an effective way to achieve the necessary complexity and scale to produce robust results.

Furthermore, while -omic technologies have a focus on risk assessment and prediction of health outcomes, for prevention to be effective, both individuals and health-systems need to change behaviours to have an impact. How to use more precise and predictive information to effectively change behaviours is not yet known and this should be the focus of a behavioural science research and innovation agenda (see challenge 10).

Considerations

A central challenge in personalised prevention is how to integrate all of these diverse fields into a coherent strategy that improves health outcomes. In terms of omics sciences, they offer enormous potential, but they also face hurdles. Omics technologies generate vast amounts of complex data, raising issues of data management such as data safety, as well as interpretation, storage, and integration into clinical practice. The potential of and requirements to integrating such data with contextual and environmental data, and the increasing amount of individual, user-generated data e.g. from wearables is one of the highlighted gaps.

More evidence is also needed to determine the accuracy and usefulness of omics data in power of predicting health outcomes in a way that can guide interventions. For example, non-genetic omics are highly sensitive to the type of analysed sample and how it has been handled (Huang, 2021). The findings from omics studies must further be proven to be valid, reliable and reproducible in real-world clinical settings, as stated in challenge 2.

These obstacles may thus hinder the ability of omics sciences to develop their full potential in personalised prevention, especially in terms of translating research into clinical practice. Among these omics, genomics is currently the most explored in personalised medicine. It has a well-established foundation in both research and clinical settings, with actionable insights already available in genetic risk assessments (Jukic, 2019; Dawed, 2023)^{33 34} Even though genomics is particularly valuable in

³³ Jukic MM, Smith RL, Haslemo T, Molden E, Ingelman-Sundberg M. Effect of CYP2D6 genotype on exposure and efficacy of risperidone and aripiprazole: a retrospective, cohort study. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2019 May;6(5):418-426. doi: 10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30088-4. Epub 2019 Apr 15.

³⁴ Dawed AY, Mari A, Brown A, McDonald TJ, Li L, Wang S, Hong MG, Sharma S, Robertson NR, Mahajan A, Wang X, Walker M, Gough S, Hart LM, Zhou K, Forgie I, Ruetten H, Pavo I, Bhatnagar P, Jones AG, Pearson ERPharmacogenomics of GLP-1 receptor agonists: a genome-wide analysis of observational data and large randomised controlled trials. DIRECT consortium. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2023 Jan;11(1):33-41. doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(22)00340-0.PMID: 36528349

advancing personalised prevention strategies, one must also consider broader socioeconomic and commercial determinants of health, such as inequalities in healthcare access, environmental conditions, in addition to the social determinants (e.g., housing, education, employment) to achieve the vision of reducing NCDs. Climate change also makes the broader determinants of health a moving target. This requires consideration of the additional utility omics offers towards realizing the potential prevention dividend.³⁵

Challenge 2: Continuous evidence synthesis system supporting personalised prevention

Status

In the past decades, numerous genetic, genomic, and more general ‘omics’ technologies have been developed, significantly enhancing the accuracy of diagnosing health conditions and providing new tools to predict disease onset and progression. Continuous evidence generation is crucial to support the implementation of personalised prevention approaches that adopt such technologies. Many studies have aimed to evaluate the ability of these tests to predict the presence or absence of specific genes, genetic variants or other biomarkers (analytical validity) and their accuracy in predicting future clinical outcomes (clinical validity). Although evidence on these dimensions, combined with safety data, may suffice to introduce a test to the market, demonstrating its clinical utility is essential for integration into personalised prevention strategies within national healthcare systems. As explained in par. 6.1, clinical utility, though not universally defined, generally refers to the test’s usefulness (or value of the information) to provide actionable information that improve patient relevant health outcomes. While analytical and clinical validity provide foundational evidence for the potential of a test, clinical utility addresses the real-world effectiveness and impact of the test on individuals’ outcomes (for instance, it is noteworthy to say that very commonly, the evidence on clinical validity of genetic tests are scanty across all the possible ancestries, that limit the transferability of evidence across populations). Demonstrating clinical utility involves proving the efficacy of the test in reducing the health burden of the condition for which it is used (clinical efficacy), as well as studying other dimensions crucial for its implementation. These include cost-effectiveness, acceptability of the test among clinicians and citizens/patients, organizational feasibility, and its impact on health

³⁵ Marin M Jukic, Robert L Smith, Tore Haslemo, Espen Molden, Magnus Ingelman-Sundberg, Effect of CYP2D6 genotype on exposure and efficacy of risperidone and aripiprazole: a retrospective, cohort study. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2019 May;6(5):418-426. doi: 10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30088-4. Epub 2019 Apr 15. PMID: 31000417, DOI: 10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30088-4

inequalities. To date, although the evaluation of these dimensions is formally required within structured evaluation frameworks, like Health Technology Assessment (HTA) or other assessment models (par. 6.1), there is a **significant lack of primary evidence** on both the **clinical efficacy** of these tests **and all other dimensions**.

Gaps

The gold standard for studying the clinical efficacy of these tests is the development of randomised controlled trials (RCTs), which are considered the highest level of evidence in the evidence pyramid, ranking just below systematic reviews and meta-analyses of RCTs³⁶. In these trials, the personalised preventive intervention (or strategy) incorporating the use of genetic or genomic tests is compared with the standard of care to assess its efficacy in improving health outcomes. RCTs are highly valued for their ability to provide the most reliable evidence of clinical efficacy due to their rigorous methodological design, which includes randomization and controlled conditions to minimise bias. However, developing such study designs is challenging in the realm of genetic and genomic medicine due to the low prevalence of specific genetic conditions, the continuous development of promising technologies that might make a trial outdated before it is terminated, and the vast combinations of gene panels and interventions that need to be studied³⁷. Moreover, limited sample sizes in trials and issues related to data sharing represent significant obstacles to achieving the statistical strength required to provide robust evidence on health outcomes. In primary and secondary prevention trials, these challenges are even more pronounced due to the substantial time lag between the implementation of the intervention and the observation of expected health outcomes, which complicates the measurement of long-term efficacy. Despite these challenges, generating solid evidence on the ability of preventive interventions that include genetic or genomics tests to reduce the health burden of these diseases remains crucial. Also, the studies on the impact of a test in terms of cost-effectiveness, patient acceptability, equity, and feasibility are likewise quite rare. One reason for this scarcity is that such evidence often necessitates prior proof of clinical efficacy, which is frequently absent or contentious. Without a solid foundation of clinical efficacy, it becomes

³⁶ Atkins D, Best D, Briss PA, Eccles M, Falck-Ytter Y, Flottorp S, Guyatt GH, Harbour RT, Haugh MC, Henry D, Hill S, Jaeschke R, Leng G, Liberati A, Magrini N, Mason J, Middleton P, Mrukowicz J, O'Connell D, Oxman AD, Phillips B, Schünemann HJ, Edejer T, Varonen H, Vist GE, Williams JW Jr, Zaza S; GRADE Working Group. Grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations. *BMJ*. 2004 Jun 19;328(7454):1490. doi: 10.1136/bmj.328.7454.1490. PMID: 15205295; PMCID: PMC428525.

³⁷ Rogowski WH, Grosse SD, Khoury MJ. Challenges of translating genetic tests into clinical and public health practice. *Nat Rev Genet*. 2009 Jul;10(7):489-95. doi: 10.1038/nrg2606. PMID: 19506575.

challenging to justify and investigate these additional dimensions. Furthermore, the study of these impacts is sometimes context-specific, requiring research within the country where the test is intended to be implemented. Variations in healthcare systems, patient populations, and socio-economic conditions mean that findings from one context may not be directly applicable to another. Hence, there is a critical need for localised studies to ensure the technology's effectiveness and relevance in the target setting. Moreover, while these domains are formally included in HTA, clear criteria for their evaluation are often lacking, leading to their underestimation in formulating recommendations. These research gaps—including the scarcity of sufficiently robust studies on clinical efficacy and the limited evaluation of broader impacts—are equally pronounced across other omics sciences, where the evidence base is even more constrained. Indeed, the mapping activities conducted within this project reveal a markedly lower volume of studies addressing clinical validity, clinical efficacy, and HTA reports in these fields compared to genetics and genomics, highlighting the need for further efforts to strengthen the evidence base in these areas.

Priorities and implementation

Strategies to study the clinical efficacy of personalised preventive approaches

Based on the considerations above on RCTs, it is essential for clinical and epidemiological expertise to assess the most suitable study design for each approach, considering both validity and feasibility. Different approaches are being developed to enhance evidence generation, particularly on genetic and genomic tests.

For example, while large-scale RCTs comparing test-based approaches with standard care are often challenging to implement, more focused RCTs can be designed to evaluate the efficacy of therapies or preventive interventions within specific risk categories identified by genetic tests. A classic example is the *BRCA1/2* test for women at risk for personalised breast and ovarian cancer prevention, recommended by major national and international guidelines. The high diagnostic accuracy of the test and the significant increase in incidence and mortality risk associated with the specific variants justified seeking the best possible evidence on the efficacy of various primary and secondary preventive interventions (such as prophylactic surgery or active surveillance) specifically in this high-

risk population³⁸. Other examples where RCTs have been implemented to study the efficacy of therapies on risk-stratified populations include the 21-Gene Expression Assay and the 70-Gene Signature for personalising breast cancer treatment. The multicenter MINDACT trial, initiated in 2007 across nine European countries, is an example of a non-inferiority RCT aimed at studying whether “high clinical risk, low genetic risk” patients have a non-inferior five-year survival without chemotherapy compared to with using it³⁹. These targeted RCTs, while still requiring significant sample sizes, long follow-up periods, and substantial costs, might represent a more practical approach than broad-based trials in the general population.

Specific considerations can also be made regarding the outcomes to be evaluated. While the final goal of any preventive intervention should be to reduce the incidence and/or mortality of a disease, intermediate endpoints can sometimes serve as effective measures for evaluating clinical efficacy. For example, the MyPeBS trial, designed to compare a personalised approach using a polygenic risk score (PRS) for breast cancer screening with the standard of care, focuses on an intermediate endpoint⁴⁰. The trial's primary objective is to assess whether the personalised approach reduces the incidence of advanced breast cancer diagnoses. While intermediate endpoints, such as reductions in late-stage diagnoses, can be useful for evaluating preventive strategies, it is crucial to ensure that these endpoints reflect an impact on the ultimate outcome of interest, such as mortality, in the context of oncological screening programmes.

Some genetic and genomic tests have been developed to enhance the effectiveness of personalised prevention strategies that have already been studied. An example is the DNA stool test, which has been introduced as a more advanced alternative to the previously used faecal occult blood test for

³⁸ Pujol P, Barberis M, Beer P, Friedman E, Piulats JM, Capoluongo ED, Garcia Foncillas J, Ray-Coquard I, Penault-Llorca F, Foulkes WD, Turnbull C, Hanson H, Narod S, Arun BK, Aapro MS, Mandel JL, Normanno N, Lambrechts D, Vergote I, Anahory M, Baertschi B, Baudry K, Bignon YJ, Bollet M, Corsini C, Cussenot O, De la Motte Rouge T, Duboys de Labarre M, Duchamp F, Duriez C, Fizazi K, Galibert V, Gladieff L, Gligorov J, Hammel P, Imbert-Bouteille M, Jacot W, Kogut-Kubiak T, Lamy PJ, Nambot S, Neuzillet Y, Olschwang S, Rebillard X, Rey JM, Rideau C, Spano JP, Thomas F, Treilleux I, Vandromme M, Vendrell J, Vintraud M, Zarca D, Hughes KS, Alés Martínez JE. Clinical practice guidelines for BRCA1 and BRCA2 genetic testing. *Eur J Cancer*. 2021 Mar;146:30-47. doi: 10.1016/j.ejca.2020.12.023. Epub 2021 Feb 10. PMID: 33578357.

³⁹ Cardoso F, van't Veer LJ, Bogaerts J, Slaets L, Viale G, Delalogue S, Pierga JY, Brain E, Causeret S, DeLorenzi M, Glas AM, Goulinopoulos V, Goulioti T, Knox S, Matos E, Meulemans B, Neijenhuis PA, Nitz U, Passalacqua R, Ravdin P, Rubio IT, Saghatchian M, Smilde TJ, Sotiriou C, Stork L, Straehle C, Thomas G, Thompson AM, van der Hoeven JM, Vuylsteke P, Bernards R, Tryfonidis K, Rutgers E, Piccart M; MINDACT Investigators. 70-Gene Signature as an Aid to Treatment Decisions in Early-Stage Breast Cancer. *N Engl J Med*. 2016 Aug 25;375(8):717-29. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1602253. PMID: 27557300.

⁴⁰ S. Delalogue, P. Giorgi Rossi, C. Balleyguier, M. Guindy, F.J. Gilbert, J-B. Burrion, M. Roman, S. de Montgolfier, L. Giordano, D. Drubay, D.G. Evans, D. Keatley, E. Gauthier, A. du Bois d'Aische, C. Baron, A. Boland, H. Blanché, D. Couch, J-F. Deleuze, S. Michiels, 135P Real-time genotyping-based breast cancer risk assessment in MyPeBS, an international randomized trial in the general population comparing risk-stratified to standard breast cancer screening (BCS), *Annals of Oncology*, Volume 33, Supplement 3, 2022, Page S184, ISSN 0923-7534, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annonc.2022.03.152>.

guiding individuals toward colonoscopy for early colorectal cancer detection⁴¹. However, while robust evidence of increased diagnostic accuracy in these trials has supported the recommendation of the DNA stool test, it is essential to conduct thorough assessments to ensure that the test's effectiveness applies to real-world clinical practice. This includes evaluating whether the test performs as expected in the target population and under routine clinical conditions.

Other strategies include the use of other methodological approaches, such as simulation models. For example, in 2021, a breast cancer simulation model developed by the Erasmus University Medical Center and the Georgetown University's Albert Einstein College of Medicine were used to evaluate the lifetime effects of different risk-tailored screening strategies⁴². A similar approach was already employed by the established Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network to develop models that were used to inform the current USPSTF breast cancer screening guidelines⁴³. These approaches generally allow direct comparisons between preventive strategies and can benefit from the use of data from biobanks or other real-world data sources. Employing these methodological approaches can enable the study of the impact of introducing genetic and genomic tests into prevention strategies. However, the evaluation of their validity and their use in generating recommendations remains a highly debated topic. The validity of the generated estimates is contingent upon the quality of the data utilized and the robustness of the models developed. First, it is necessary to ensure transparency and reproducibility of the models; then, clear methods for assessing the model estimates are necessary. These methods should set standards for evaluating the credibility of the models, which are prone to bias since bias can arise from the input data and during the model calibration and validation phases⁴⁴.

Generating primary evidence on all the dimensions of clinical utility

⁴¹ Imperiale TF, Porter K, Zella J, Gagrat ZD, Olson MC, Statz S, Garces J, Lavin PT, Aguilar H, Brinberg D, Berkelhammer C, Kisiel JB, Limburg PJ; BLUE-C Study Investigators. Next-Generation Multitarget Stool DNA Test for Colorectal Cancer Screening. *N Engl J Med*. 2024 Mar 14;390(11):984-993. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2310336. PMID: 38477986.

⁴² Van den Broek JJ, Schechter CB, van Ravesteyn NT, Janssens ACJW, Wolfson MC, Trentham-Dietz A, Simard J, Easton DF, Mandelblatt JS, Kraft P, de Koning HJ. Personalizing Breast Cancer Screening Based on Polygenic Risk and Family History. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2021 Apr 6;113(4):434-442. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djaa127. PMID: 32853342; PMCID: PMC8599807.

⁴³ Henderson JT, Webber EM, Weyrich MS, Miller M, Melnikow J. Screening for Breast Cancer: Evidence Report and Systematic Review for the US Preventive Services Task Force. *JAMA*. 2024;331(22):1931–1946. doi:10.1001/jama.2023.25844

⁴⁴ Brozek JL, Canelo-Aybar C, Akl EA, Bowen JM, ...and Schünemann HJ; GRADE Working GRADE Guidelines 30: the GRADE approach to assessing the certainty of modeled evidence-An overview in the context of health decision-making. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021 Jan;129:138-150. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.09.018. Epub 2020 Sep 24. PMID: 32980429; PMCID: PMC8514123.

To reduce the gap in evidence regarding the impact of the tests on various dimensions like cost-effectiveness, patient acceptability, equity, ethical aspects and feasibility, it is essential to invest in responsible research and innovation in this field. Funding programmes should allocate resources not only to clinical efficacy studies but also to investigations focusing on these broader impacts.⁴⁵ Certain dimensions of technology impact can be evaluated within the context of clinical trials designed to assess clinical efficacy. For example, incorporating patient-reported outcomes (PROs) into these trials can provide valuable insights into patient acceptability and quality of life. Similarly, assessing the experiences and feedback of clinicians during these studies can shed light on feasibility and practical implementation challenges.

Synthesise and evaluate evidence quality

In order to implement effective personalised prevention approaches, a priority should be to ensure that the evidence produced is synthesised and that clear criteria for evaluating the quality and robustness of evidence are applied. These criteria must evaluate the quality of evidence, including its validity, study design, and potential implementation levels. Based on the level of evidence, the output of the synthesis should be categorised according to different levels of strength. Moreover, the scientific merit of testing technologies in personalised prevention depends on incorporating standardised methods for quality control, clinical validity, and overall utility. Ensuring that all testing technologies adhere to high standards is essential for producing reliable and actionable evidence.

To standardise and share it is necessary to invest in a system specifically designed to systematically synthesise evidence, ensuring that each piece of evidence is categorised based on its quality. This could be a dynamic, unified repository modelled on successful frameworks such as the U.S. CDC's Center for Precision Public Health, which utilises a tiered classification system for genomic medicine guidelines⁴⁶. The system should allow for continuous updates as new evidence emerges, facilitating easy access to and retrieval of information.

Such a repository would serve as a valuable resource for healthcare professionals, policymakers, and researchers by providing a clear and structured overview of the evidence. This would support more

⁴⁵ Marschalek, I., Handler, K., Hofer, M., Schrammel, M., Unterfrauner, E. (2020). Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): A Critical Reflection Toward Evaluation Standards. In: Carayannis, E.G. (eds) Encyclopedia of Creativity, Invention, Innovation and Entrepreneurship. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-15347-6_200035

⁴⁶ Center for Disease Control and Prevention, Work in Progress: Classifying Evidence-based Genomic Applications for Practice and Prevention, Available at https://blogs.cdc.gov/genomics/2018/02/28/work_in_progress/, Accessed on 25/07/24

informed decision-making and ultimately enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of preventive healthcare interventions.

Health Systems Integration

Health systems face numerous challenges when attempting to integrate and deliver personalised prevention approaches that are adapted to diverse local contexts. One of the primary obstacles is the creation of assessment tools that are tailored to the specific needs and structures of each healthcare system. The complexity of designing evaluation frameworks that account for local epidemiology, resources, and healthcare infrastructure means that a one-size-fits-all solution is rarely feasible. Moreover, the challenge of data sharing is significant, as the effectiveness of personalised prevention relies on access to large, diverse datasets to enhance the accuracy of evaluations and evidence generation. Ensuring interoperability between different health systems, while safeguarding patient privacy and data security, is a critical hurdle. This lack of unified data can slow the development of robust methodologies for assessing new omic technologies, ultimately hindering their adoption. Therefore, fostering collaboration across regions and countries, and developing standardised yet flexible frameworks, is essential for realising the potential of personalised prevention in different healthcare settings.

Considerations

As we advance the integration of genetic and genomic tests into personalised prevention strategies, several critical considerations must be addressed to ensure their success and sustainability. It is essential to recognise the rapid pace of technological advancements in genetics and genomics, necessitating continuous evidence synthesis efforts and regular updates to evaluation frameworks and assessment guidelines. This dynamic landscape requires a flexible approach to research and policy-making, ensuring that emerging evidence is swiftly incorporated into practice.

Investing in primary research by funding studies that are both feasible and effective in evaluating clinical efficacy is necessary. These studies should be designed considering the progressive steps needed for implementation from bench to public health practice. While expert matter knowledge is necessary to ensure the accurate and comprehensive assessment of the intended outcomes, such implementation considerations are crucial to ensure that the studies are appropriately tailored to

respond to the correct questions along the translational spectrum. Furthermore, additional primary studies are needed in the other omics sciences, which, while promising, still lack sufficient evidence, limiting their broader implementation and integration into clinical practice.

At the same time, it is important to establish clear parameters for evaluating this evidence. Creating standardised evaluation criteria will help ensure that the results of these studies are consistently and transparently assessed, facilitating their integration into healthcare decision-making processes. This combined approach of robust primary research and clear evaluative frameworks will support the effective implementation of personalised prevention strategies.

Challenge 3: The PROPHET Framework implementation

Status

Since the early 2000s, various frameworks have been developed to evaluate the clinical utility of genetic and genomic tests. Despite many efforts, there is still no widely accepted criteria for evaluating preventive approaches that use genetic and genomic technologies. This lack of standardised criteria has caused inconsistencies in how different countries and regions evaluate and implement these technologies. Moreover, the varied methodologies and evaluation criteria in different frameworks have led to a fragmented understanding of clinical utility, making it harder to make informed decisions about adopting genomic technologies in healthcare systems, especially in resource-limited settings.

In 2021, the European Union made significant progress by approving a new HTA regulation⁴⁷. The regulation aims to encourage streamlining of the assessment process, allowing member states to evaluate jointly the clinical data and evidence submitted for a health technology. This aims to address the lack of consistent methodology and processes across EU Member States, which leads to considerable variation in the evaluation of vaccines, drugs, and medical devices. The new regulation,

⁴⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2021 on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU (Text with EEA relevance), available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2282>, accessed on 25/07/24.

set to be fully implemented by January 2025, marks a crucial step towards more unified and consistent assessments of health technologies across Europe.

Gaps

Despite the progress made with the new HTA regulation, significant gaps remain in the evaluation of genetic and genomic tests. One major challenge is the lack of primary evidence that informs any assessment, which makes it difficult to obtain informed decisions about adopting and implementing these technologies. This issue is compounded by the absence of consensus on the dimensions and indicators that should be used for recommendations. Without agreed-upon criteria, standardising evaluations and ensuring all relevant aspects is tough⁴⁸.

Moreover, the HTA has traditionally focused on evaluating the clinical efficacy and cost-effectiveness of tests, often overlooking or undervaluing other potential impacts that implementing a genetic or genomic technology can have⁴⁹. Although clinical efficacy is a *conditio sine qua non* for assessing any test, the effective implementation of personalised preventive approaches also requires recognising that the decreasing costs of omics-based tests and data integration platforms call for a more dynamic consideration of economic evidence. Overemphasizing cost-effectiveness, without accounting for evolving cost trends, risks creating unnecessary barriers to the adoption of personalised preventive approaches. In this regard, modelling approaches should consider incorporating declining cost functions or, where appropriate, applying a specific discount rate to reflect the expected reduction in technological costs over time.

Effective implementation therefore requires a comprehensive evaluation framework that, alongside cost-effectiveness, also integrates factors such as feasibility, allocative value, patient acceptability, the personal value of the test information, legitimacy, and equity. These dimensions are often context-specific and can vary significantly across different countries and populations.

Priorities and implementation

⁴⁸ Hoxhaj I, Govaerts L, Simoens S, Van Dyck W, Huys I, Gutiérrez-Ibarluzea I, et al. A Systematic Review of the Value Assessment Frameworks Used within Health Technology Assessment of Omics Technologies and Their Actual Adoption from HTA Agencies. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(21). Mario cosa è successo non ha il suo numeretto

⁴⁹ Love-Koh J, Peel A, Rejon-Parrilla JC, Ennis K, Lovett R, Manca A, et al. The Future of Precision Medicine: Potential Impacts for Health Technology Assessment. *Pharmacoeconomics*. 2018;36(12):1439-51.

The PROPHET framework aims to address the aforementioned gaps by providing a holistic approach when evaluating and implementing personalised preventive approaches. This framework includes all relevant aspects - professionals, tools, technology, resources, clinical and community pathways - to ensure a thorough and comprehensive appraisal of these approaches thanks to a full stakeholder engagement process. The goal is to guide public health authorities in adopting personalised preventive approaches using both health system and value-based perspectives.

The PROPHET framework builds on the HTA model promoted by the new European regulation, which mandates a joint assessment of the efficacy and safety of the technology at the European level and an evaluation of context-specific dimensions, such as economic aspects, feasibility, and acceptability at the national level (for further details please refer to Appendix 1, Section 9.2). To comprehensively evaluate a personalised prevention approach, it is essential to ensure not only that the impact of the test on these dimensions is assessed, but also that these evaluations are conducted in collaboration with all stakeholder groups and are structurally considered when providing recommendations on implementation. The experience of using Health Impact Assessment (HIA) for non-health related policies provides valuable insights for a more holistic and context-specific evaluation of personalised prevention approaches^{50,51}. In the context of genetic and genomic tests, these policies relate to determining the reimbursability of such tests and establishing the pathways for these decisions within the health system. Additionally they may include requirements for mandatory testing prior to specific medical interventions for making a test mandatory before certain medical interventions can be undertaken, similar to the model used for abacavir (drug used for the treatment of AIDS, based on a genetic testing before treatment). This approach will therefore improve equity in access to genetic and genomic tests. The HIA model emphasises the importance of structured and meaningful engagement of stakeholders throughout the evaluation process. This includes healthcare professionals, patients, policymakers, and community representatives, whose perspectives and concerns are vital for a thorough assessment. By involving these stakeholders, the evaluation process can capture a wide range of impacts and ensure that the outcomes are relevant and acceptable to all parties involved.

⁵⁰ Harris-Roxas, B., Viliani, F., Bond, A., Cave, B., Divall, M., Furu, P., ... Winkler, M. (2012). Health impact assessment: the state of the art. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 30(1), 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2012.666035>

⁵¹ Ádám B, Lovas S, Ádány R. Use of Genomic Information in Health Impact Assessment is Yet to Come: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 Dec 15;17(24):9417. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17249417. PMID: 33334033; PMCID: PMC7765467.

Furthermore, the HIA model requires a comprehensive consideration of impacts, including factors that are often overlooked, such as health inequalities. This approach allows for a broader assessment that goes beyond the immediate clinical and economic impacts of the test to include its effects on different population groups and social determinants of health. For instance, understanding how a new genetic test might be perceived by different communities, its accessibility, and how it might exacerbate or mitigate health disparities is crucial for its successful implementation.

Additionally, HIA provides robust methodologies for developing programs that ensure the effective implementation and continuous monitoring of policies. This includes setting up systems for regular review and feedback, allowing for ongoing improvements based on new evidence and changing circumstances. The continuous monitoring aspect is particularly important as it helps identify any unintended consequences early on and provides opportunities to address them promptly.

In conclusion, the PROPHET Framework enhances the structured HTA evaluation implemented by the new European regulation with elements of HIA and a more structured monitoring plan. Implementing such comprehensive evaluations is undoubtedly complex and requires significant coordination and resources. Despite these challenges, our project has demonstrated that conducting these comprehensive evaluations is feasible within constrained budgets through three case studies in different countries and examining different tests and related policies.⁵² This approach ensures a more holistic and continuous evaluation of personalised prevention approaches.

Considerations

The development and implementation of the PROPHET framework should consider several critical factors:

- For new in vitro devices or diagnostic tests, it would be beneficial to establish a voluntary early engagement mechanism involving HTA bodies, public health authorities, and developers. This mechanism would allow for early dialogue to jointly define evidence requirements, exchange expertise, and coordinate study designs,

⁵² Valz Gris, A., Kannan, P., Costa, A., de Fátima Silva Lopes, M., Cardoso, M. L., Pezzullo, A., ... & Boccia, S. (2024). Health Impact Assessment in Personalized Prevention: three applications on pharmacogenomic testing. *European Journal of Public Health*, 34(Supplement_3), ckac144-1576.

fostering alignment and efficiency in generating evidence to support both national and regional decision-making.

- **Regulatory Alignment:** It is essential to align the evaluations with the new HTA regulation, focusing on centralised clinical data assessment while addressing national context-specific impacts. This alignment ensures consistency and reliability in the evaluation process, and emphasises the importance of always using standardised and transparent methodologies to guarantee comparability and scientific robustness across assessments. Even when the evaluation does not fall directly under the HTA framework, for example, when it concerns broader public health programs or interventions rather than specific technologies, it remains important to ensure methodological consistency and to apply standardized approaches to maintain quality, transparency, and reliability of the assessment process.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Effective involvement of stakeholders in the evaluation process is crucial to ensure that all relevant impacts, particularly those related to inequalities, are considered. Stakeholders should be engaged in a structured manner to provide valuable insights and enhance the legitimacy of the evaluation process.
- **Comprehensive Evaluation:** The evaluation should use methodologies that incorporate both health system and value-based perspectives. This approach ensures a thorough assessment of personalised preventive approaches, considering all relevant dimensions and impacts.
- **Policy Monitoring and Adaptation:** Establishing programs for continuous monitoring and adaptation of policies is critical to ensure their effectiveness and relevance over time. These programs should include mechanisms for regular review and adjustment based on new evidence and changing contexts.

By addressing these considerations, the PROPHET framework can provide a robust and holistic approach to evaluating and implementing personalised preventive approaches.

Challenge 4: Data collection and integration, and Data Infrastructure

Status

A substantial increase in the creation of life sciences data has enhanced our understanding of disease

risk, paving the way for preventative healthcare. To harness the potential of this data for personalised preventative medicine, integrating life science data is essential, drawing from previous European experiences, and co-creating with other sectors. Lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrate the value of using unified frameworks and data-sharing structures.⁵³ Research Infrastructures like ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, and EuroBioimaging have made progress, yet further efforts and investment are needed with a focus on three core areas: data quality and collection, data integration, and data infrastructure.

Healthcare-generated data, often clinical or ad-hoc, is typically not reusable. To overcome fragmented data collection it is crucial to identify and implement best practices using proven models as examples. Initiatives like Genomics England and disease registries (ERN-RND, The Danish Cancer Registry) aim to make clinical and genomic data accessible for research. Efforts in research and clinical-research settings have improved data management for access and reuse. Biobanks (e.g. The Estonian Biobank⁵⁴ and FinnGen⁵⁵ both part of the BBMRI-ERIC network) and repositories (e.g. the European Genome Phenome Archive (EGA)⁵⁶) help support studies like Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) investigating genetic disease components, aiding in polygenic risk score modelling for preventative approaches. However, it is not easy to extract actionable information immediately from omics data, as the complexity and variability of genomic data require significant curation, interpretation, and integration with other data types to yield meaningful insights.

The 1+MG initiative and the Genome of Europe project aim to unify national cohorts of genomic sequencing data, creating a key tool for understanding genetic disease drivers. However, fragmented, inaccessible, and inconsistent-quality data, especially from diverse sources such as socioeconomic, behavioral, and lifestyle data, present challenges for creating fully integrated, personalised preventive interventions⁵⁷. Organisations such as GA4GH are working to cultivate a common framework of standards and harmonised approaches for effective and responsible sharing of genomic and related health data⁵⁸.

⁵³ Collins FS, Varmus H. A new initiative on precision medicine. *N Engl J Med*. 2015 Feb 26;372(9):793-5. doi: 10.1056/NEJMp1500523. Epub 2015 Jan 30. PMID: 25635347; PMCID: PMC5101938.

⁵⁴ The Estonian Biobank: From Cohorts to Personalised Medicine" (*Journal of Translational Medicine*, 2019). Available at: <https://translational-medicine.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12967-019-1977-4>

⁵⁵ FinnGen: A Comprehensive Database for Genomic and Health Data from Finland" (*European Journal of Human Genetics*, 2020). Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41431-020-00782-5>

⁵⁶ <https://ega-archive.org/>

⁵⁷ Lovestone, S. (2020). The European Medical Information Framework: A novel ecosystem for sharing healthcare data across Europe. *Learning Health Systems*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/lrh2.10214>

⁵⁸ GA4GH: International policies and standards for data sharing across genomic research and healthcare" (*Nature Reviews Genetics*, 2020). Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41576-019-0170-0>

While substantial progress has been made, infrastructure and federated analysis tools at national and European levels remain insufficient for complex data integration—particularly with non-health data like behavioral and lifestyle variables, increasingly captured by personal devices, wearables, and lifestyle apps. These data types require distinct privacy, consent, and quality considerations, and their integration with health and genomic data demands robust data harmonisation and governance frameworks. Standardised platforms inspired by successful commercial models are urgently needed to help healthcare providers and researchers navigate and share data responsibly while respecting patient consent. Frameworks like OMOP and HL7 FHIR are promising but require broader implementation, particularly as international and EU regulations evolve. With the exception of the BBMRI-ERIC Federated Platform, currently, national and European infrastructure and federated analysis tools are not advanced to deal with complex data integration and data coming from different sectors and sustained data infrastructure is limited. The European Health Data Space (EHDS), Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), and EUCAIM aim to integrate data and develop infrastructure that fits the necessary technical and ELSI requirements. Within GDI⁵⁹ 15 countries have committed to establish a national node to manage human genomic data by 2026.

Gaps

Within the realm of healthcare data management, several significant gaps continue to pose challenges. One of the primary issues is the lack of standardization. The absence of widely accepted standards creates a fragmented ecosystem, which complicates the integration of data across different systems. It is necessary to consider how data from a wide range of biomarkers, including genomics, can be integrated and used to drive the development of personalised prevention interventions, and this fragmentation makes it difficult for researchers and healthcare providers to effectively work together and share information. The adoption of "minimal data sets" that distinguish "must-have" data from "nice-to-have" data is essential for guiding collection practices for both research and healthcare. To fully support prevention, consistent and longitudinal data collection needs to be supported, particularly from individuals when they are healthy, otherwise datasets will only address ongoing health challenges, rather than being useful to support prevention by flagging changes that may be indicative of the early development of disease. To address this issue, emerging standards like OMOP and HL7 FHIR hold great promise, yet they require broader implementation to truly make an impact,

⁵⁹ European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project (onemilliongenomes.eu)

especially as new standards arise to accommodate multi-sectoral data integration. Another major hurdle is the challenge of data discoverability. The HDR-UK health data gateway is an example of an initiative to tackle many of these challenges⁶⁰. Researchers often struggle to find relevant datasets due to the fragmentation of resources, poor data quality, and inconsistent data management practices. While the establishment of unified health and genomic records could significantly enhance discoverability, there are still many barriers to their effective implementation. Furthermore, the situation is made more complex when we consider the integration of data from sectors beyond healthcare, including socioeconomic and environmental data, which only adds to the challenge due to variations in data structure, privacy concerns, and the contextual nature of these variables.

Accessing health and genomic data is critical for the advancement of personalised prevention and medicine. However, several obstacles continue to limit this access. Regulatory requirements can be daunting and create unnecessary hurdles, while the general lack of digital health literacy complicates the necessary administrative processes surrounding consent procedures and data-sharing policies. Additionally, the availability of high-quality data is often scarce, which underscores the need for clearer guidelines and practices that could facilitate better access.

Data reproducibility presents yet another challenge in this landscape. Gaps in quality assurance and the absence of comprehensive metadata can significantly impede research reproducibility, which in turn limits the applicability of research findings within clinical settings.

Moreover, effective data use mandates robust infrastructure and stringent security measures. For data to be integrated successfully into clinical environments, it must align with existing regulatory requirements, which is essential for safeguarding patient information.

Finally, translating research into clinical practice is not without its challenges. This process necessitates specialised training, fostering collaboration across various sectors, and ensuring alignment with regulatory processes. Additionally, it also requires the necessary tools and training for healthcare professionals to use whilst providing patient care. Addressing these multifaceted issues is crucial for unlocking the full potential of health and genomic data, ultimately enhancing patient care and outcomes.

Priorities and Implementation

- Standardisation: Implement standardised practices at both international and national level as

⁶⁰ <https://healthdatagateway.org/en>

recommended in the 1+MG Framework and supported by global and EU standards by GA4GH and ISO, for data structure and standardisation in health systems to overcome challenges arising from the use of unstructured formats and competing standards.

- **Discoverability:** Develop unified health and genomic records, as best practices, to enhance data discoverability at local, regional, national, and eventually international level. Efforts should focus on creating tools and platforms that facilitate easy and effective search and validation of appropriate datasets.
- **Accessibility:** Address variations in data accessibility across nations by establishing clearer and consistent regulations and consent mechanisms.
- **Reproducibility:** Ensure the availability of high-quality datasets with comprehensive metadata. Attention should be given to addressing metadata gaps for different types of health data to support research, regulatory purposes, and personalised prevention methods⁶¹.
- **Data Sharing:** Establish secure approaches to data sharing, addressing reidentification and privacy concerns, ensuring patient and data safety at all times. Encourage organisations to adopt best practices for data sharing and enhanced digital health literacy to improve collaborative efforts.
- **Data integration:** Ensuring that data integration adheres to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles is crucial. This involves creating secure, standardised, and interoperable services under a common framework that respects jurisdictional boundaries for datasets while centralising and making metadata discoverable through common APIs. Multisectoral data integration: integrating socioeconomic and contextual data on e.g. environments need development.

Considerations

To realise preventive medicine, there is a need to systematically connect and access population, clinical, genomic, and lifestyle data to perform research at a larger scale. Due to the heterogeneity of clinical data, sustained curation and accessible research data are critical. The use of standards like Beacon V2 (being expanded to support DICOM queries) will facilitate the generation of virtual cohorts for linking data across different modalities. The utilisation of interoperable metadata models,

⁶¹ Kho, A. N., Rasmussen, L. V., Connolly, J. J., Peissig, P. L., Starren, J., Hakonarson, H., ... & Roden, D. M. (2019). Practical challenges in integrating genomic data into the electronic health record. *Genetics in Medicine*, 21(9), 1918-1927.

data standards and semantic annotation will facilitate data analysis and training of AI models across different modalities of data and data sources.

To implement the infrastructure and data management required, capacity needs to be increased for the five functionalities of data management: data discovery, data reception, storage and interfaces, data access management, and processing. Additionally, infrastructure in the healthcare setting needs to be interoperable with the research domain, paying particular attention to cybersecurity and privacy. Capacity development in data discovery, reception, storage, access, and processing is necessary, particularly as AI/ML-driven prevention models become more prevalent. To support actionable insights, investment in clinician-friendly tools is vital so that providers can interpret validated models for personalised prevention.

Interdisciplinary cooperation is needed to set shared data standards, reduce bureaucratic obstacles, and enhance healthcare efficiency.

Challenge 5: Community Engagement and trust

Status

Personalised medicine and prevention, in which genomic information plays an important role, envisions and requires active and informed patients and citizens who take an active role in managing their own health and care. They need to be well-informed to be empowered to make decisions regarding their health and prevention that reflect their personal values, and be aware of options for contributing to research, such as via data sharing⁶². However, what such engagement and empowerment entails may differ per domain relevant for personalised prevention: research, care or governance. To this end, we are aware that at the population level, 40% of health outcomes depend on socioeconomic status, with education playing a major role. This is why increasing health literacy in general, and in (personal) prevention is an asset. In research, patients with personal experience of a disease offer a unique perspective that, if explicitly incorporated, leads to science that is more relevant and translatable. Roles may range from “passive” study participants to “active” patients and the public being involved in all phases of research. In the care domain, individuals should feel empowered to make optimal decisions regarding their health and prevention that align with their personal values and preferences, leading to more culturally sensitive and patient-centred care. The

⁶² www.EPPERMED.eu

governance domain emphasises the involvement of the public and patients in decision-making processes regarding personalised prevention policies and programs, encompassing their participation in policy development, guideline formulation, and organisational governance structures.

For citizens and patients to become active partners in prevention, they must be systematically and meaningfully engaged in the planning, delivery and evaluation of these three domains.^{63,64} In recent years a range of instruments has been developed for engaging and empowering citizens and patients in various ways and to various degrees, ranging from one-directional methods, such as interviews to more collaborative participation in patient forums. Currently the former instruments are more frequently reported than the latter. The effectiveness and outcomes of engagement are often not measured.

Gaps

- Studies and reviews consistently report a lack of knowledge among citizens and patients regarding genetic information, while new concepts such as personalised medicine are not well-known. Lack of awareness and potential benefits may hinder acceptance and implementation of personalised prevention.
- Health care providers can help patients navigate genomic and personalised information, but often are also not sufficiently educated on these topics, and lack time for such additional tasks.
- Though elements of good engagement practices are more widely recognised (e.g. meaningful engagement needs iterative or continuous involvement, support and remuneration for patient input), evaluation towards specific goals for engagement is often lacking or patchy.
- Meaningful engagement requires dedicated funding and resources.
- Multisectoral governance poses a gap in community engagement as it requires effective coordination and communication between diverse sectors, such as healthcare, education, and policy-making, which often have different priorities and operating structures. This fragmentation can lead to inconsistent messaging, delayed decision-making, and challenges

⁶³ Menear M, Girard A, Dugas M, Gervais M, Gilbert M, Gagnon MP. Personalised care planning and shared decision making in collaborative care programs for depression and anxiety disorders: A systematic review. PLoS One. 2022 Jun 10;17(6):e0268649. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0268649. PMID: 35687610; PMCID: PMC9187074.

⁶⁴ Schuster AL, Hampel H, Paskett ED, Bridges JF. Rethinking patient engagement in cancer research. The Patient-Patient-Centered Outcomes Research. 2023;16(2):89-93.

in aligning goals, ultimately hindering meaningful and cohesive community involvement. Bridging this gap requires creating unified strategies that foster collaboration across sectors while ensuring that community voices are adequately represented.

Priorities and implementation:

- Co-create with Citizens and Patients: engage citizens and patients through their organizations (NGOs and Patient Advocacy Groups) in co-designing personalised prevention policies, decision-making processes, and communication activities. This engagement is essential for addressing public concerns, fostering trust, and ensuring that prevention strategies are aligned with the needs of the individuals and communities.
- Enhancing Community Engagement: Prioritise and improve community engagement, as defined by the WHO: “a process of developing relationships that enable stakeholders to work together to address health-related issues and promote well-being to achieve positive health impact and outcomes.” This approach is fundamental to the successful implementation of personalised prevention strategies.⁶⁵ Need to support the active participation of community in awareness campaigns, prevention programs, and research initiatives.
- Generate more structural funding for citizen and patient engagement in research, care and public health, and their governance. Education and raising awareness of options for personalised prevention and taking part in health research.
- Amplify lived-experience stories (with consent) from patients/citizens via community ambassadors and multimedia campaigns to build trust and illustrate prevention benefits, ensuring diversity and avoiding overpromising.
- Develop and study online information and communication tools to disseminate knowledge on genetic testing and preventive options for citizens, patients, and their family members.

Considerations

⁶⁵ WHO community engagement framework for quality, people-centred and resilient health services”, <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/259280/WHO-HIS-SDS-2017.15-eng.pdf>

- Currently more engagement practices focus on care and research by patients, rather than citizens. Citizens may be more difficult to reach and may need other information tools. Awareness of prevention may also be more prominent in school curricula.
- Accessibility of information might be an issue: online tools for information and communication may be difficult to access and understand for persons with low digital literacy and health literacy, potentially exacerbating health inequalities. More specific attention to inform and engage such persons may be needed, e.g. by using more images for clarity and trustworthiness, as well as other individuals and communities that are marginalised or vulnerable and may have less access to or more distrust towards (health) institutions.
- Personal contact with and information by health professionals may increase trust in personalised prevention and data sharing, and such contact with e.g. primary care physicians and pharmacists would be also easily accessible for citizens.
- Robust structures for responsible health data sharing data may boost trustworthiness (see also Challenges 3 on Infrastructure and 9 on ELSI)
- As research and care become more interconnected, good communication to patients and citizens is necessary to help them understand what they can and cannot expect from their contribution in regard to their own health and prevention.

Challenge 6: Health Professionals and Policy Makers involvement

Status

At an institutional, national and international level, both health professionals and policymakers are essential in enabling the implementation of personalised preventive approaches in healthcare systems. Collaboration among stakeholders is critical to address regulatory, resource, and technological challenges. Policymakers should be encouraged to use stakeholder input and evidence-based research to guide their decisions. Ultimately, policymakers have the potential to create and support robust infrastructures and responsible practices that drive meaningful change towards a future healthcare system in which the overall strategy focuses not only on treatment but also on prevention. Through engagement and collaboration, barriers to implementation can be overcome, resulting in a healthcare system that is more personalised, preventive, patient-centred and supported by the public.

Capacity building, education and information are important elements of engagement: well-informed policymakers and health professionals are better equipped to draft and discuss policies regarding personalised prevention with other relevant stakeholders and sustain further responsible implementation across disciplines, domains and national borders.

A variety of policymakers should be distinguished because they have different roles and responsibilities regarding aspects of personalised prevention, as they influence research agendas, funding priorities, guideline development, education, and the implementation of clinical innovations. Their educational needs may differ accordingly. For instance, professional organisations of medical specialists decide on guidelines for implementation of specific tests, public health (screening) organisations may decide on e.g. stratification of screening programmes based on biomarkers, governmental HTA organisations may decide on the thresholds for added value used in the assessment, reimbursement experts may decide on economic aspects. Key components of this engagement include capacity building, education, and access to accurate information. This process also necessitates addressing diverse and sometimes conflicting professional interests. Engaging stakeholders within and outside the HIA exercises, and fostering dialogue are vital for sound policymaking, enhancing public trust in data sharing, and supporting the ethical implementation of personalised prevention.

Increasingly, education on genomics (as a tool in personalised prevention) focusses not only on genetic experts, including clinical geneticists, genetic nurses⁶⁶ and genetic counselors, but also on non-genetic health care professionals. In primary and secondary care well-trained health professionals, such as general practitioners, nurses, pharmacists or pediatricians will be able to inform citizens and patients on personalized prevention options. The number of education initiatives targeting policy makers in public health programmes is limited. As a good example, USA cancer programmes (integrating a.o. *BRCA* testing) illustrate how state cancer genetics programs have partnered with cancer registries, clinical facilities, health-care providers, health systems, public and private payers, policymakers, other state, regional, and federal programs, academic institutions,

⁶⁶ Association of Genetic Nurses and Counsellors (AGNC). Professional Development Framework for Genetic Nurses and Counsellors in the United Kingdom and Ireland. AGNC, 2018.

community organisations, advocacy groups, and industry.⁶⁷ Empowered, well-trained clinicians become “clinical champions” who advocate for and normalize personalised prevention in their organisations.⁶⁸

Gaps

- Knowledge on economic models that assess cost-effectiveness of personalised prevention is lacking. Resources for and education on HTA are thus needed.
- In assessing the evolving landscape of educational initiatives for non-genetic health professionals relevant for personalised prevention in healthcare, several gaps have surfaced:
 - ✓ Appropriate training is required to increase genetic literacy among healthcare professionals to allow for effective information provision and counselling of patients, patient support, referral and efficient stratification in public health screening.
 - ✓ There is a need for training in new categories such as somatic genomics related to the tumour.
 - ✓ Introduction of new methods of assessment of competences such as Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) will allow for a focus on applying knowledge and know-how in addition to know-what.
 - ✓ Incorporation of public and patient involvement in education for health professionals.

Priorities and implementation

It is important to train healthcare professionals in personalised medicine, but also in epidemiology and statistics so that they can understand the concept of risk and determinants of health in a broader context, also including environmental and climate challenges, and properly communicate health risks

⁶⁷ Green 2019

⁶⁸ Monahan KJ, Ryan N, Monje-Garcia L, Armstrong R, Church DN, Cook J, Elghobashy A, Lalloo F, Lane S, McDermott FD, Miles T, Hardy SA, Tyson A, Wang VYW, Kim A, Gelinas S, Faravelli F, Elmslie F, Shaw AC. The English National Lynch Syndrome transformation project: an NHS Genomic Medicine Service Alliance (GMSA) programme. *BMJ Oncol.* 2023 Oct 30;2(1):e000124. doi: 10.1136/bmjonc-2023-000124. PMID: 39886501; PMCID: PMC11315360.

to citizens and patients. The new generation of health care professionals, but also those in the workforce aged 50 and more, need to understand the concept of personalised prevention, be aware of the available approaches, and be aware of the relevance of data collection and use in health. Health systems might want to expand arrangements, for instance, via dedicated professionals such as nurses or screening programmes, to explicitly assign responsibility for risk communication, with clear referral pathways and documentation standards.

A very important aspect is to allow health professionals time for professional education and shared decision making. This can take the form of protected clinical time (and reimbursement) for healthcare professionals to complete training and conduct shared decision-making conversations. Also, health systems should make these things easy for general practitioners without overburdening them.^{69 70} An “enhanced” patient-doctor relationship is key to supporting behavioural change and ensuring patients have the information they need to make informed decisions about their health⁷¹. Health systems might also seed clinician-champion networks and encourage peer-to-peer training within professionals societies. In 2026, the PROPHET project will publish the Action Plans for the uptake of the PROPHET framework, fostering engagement and capacity building for health professionals and policy makers. A toolbox for capacity building will be developed, including a range of materials for the various types of health professionals and policymakers. It will include factsheets, policy briefs, webinars, conference presentations. It is important to link to other initiatives and existing information materials and online tools also for non-genetic health professionals that are made available by e.g. professional organisations and citizen and patient organisations⁷²

In terms of the topics to be covered, the capacity building will need to include ethical and legal aspects related to big data and data infrastructures, evaluation of clinical utility including cost effectiveness, and pathways for prevention and treatment.

Consideration

To support personalised prevention in our European health and care systems, health care professionals and policymakers need to be engaged and therefore have specific training. Education can take the

69 Martin SA, Johansson M, Heath I, Lehman R, Korownyk C. Sacrificing patient care for prevention: distortion of the role of general practice. *BMJ*. 2025 Jan 21;388:e080811. doi: 10.1136/bmj-2024-080811. PMID: 39837625.

70 Gray M. Prevention in primary care: more of the same is not the answer. *BMJ*. 2025 Mar 5;388:r413. doi: 10.1136/bmj.r413. PMID: 40044229.

71 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5296930/>

72 European Society of Human Genetics: Genetic Educational Materials and Sources:

mode of face-to-face training sessions but, given the large number and variety of policymakers and health care professionals involved, online training modules and materials are increasingly more effective in disseminating knowledge. Further research is necessary to evaluate training modes and materials for specific purposes and target groups. More time and facilitation for health professionals to complete training and shared decision making is a resourcing requirement.

It is to be expected that clinical geneticists will play an important part in being available for advice and coaching other professionals on more complex health problems.⁷³ The fields of public health and genetics may be separated by different traditions and practices (e.g. regarding prevention, screening, and one-size-fits-all approaches), requiring time for alignment and integration.

Challenge 7: Regulatory aspects and synergy with private sector

Status

The implementation of prevention strategies requires synergy between public and private sectors. Public-private partnerships (PPP) are important for utilising the strengths and capabilities of businesses. These partnerships involve shared investments in research and development initiatives leveraging the strengths and resources of both sectors to address health challenges and create targeted measures.

Engaging with the private sector plays a role in advancing personalised prevention for various reasons:

- **Innovation and Technological Advancements:** Private firms, such as those specialising in biotechnology and health technology can lead the way in applying innovation. Their contributions, such as cutting-edge tools like wearable health devices and genomic technologies have great potential for prevention efforts.
- **Data Handling:** Successful personalised prevention initiatives heavily depend on data collection, integration and analysis. Private sector organisations possess the infrastructure and

⁷³ Tobias ES, Avram E, Calapod P, Cordier C, den Dunnen JT, Ding C, Dolzan V, Houge SD, Lynch SA, O'Byrne J, Patsalis P, Prokopenko I, Soares CA, Tobias AP, Newman WG. The Role of the European Society of Human Genetics in Delivering Genomic Education. *Front Genet.* 2021 Sep 3;12:693952. doi: 10.3389/fgene.2021.693952. PMID: 34539735; PMCID: PMC8446627.

expertise for sophisticated data management including utilising artificial intelligence (AI) to extract valuable insights from health data. A comprehensive data strategy may include gathering and integrating various types of information, such as personal device data (e.g., physical activity, heart rate, and sleep metrics from wearables); environmental data (e.g., air quality, noise, and access to green spaces); school data on nutrition and mental health; technical diagnostic data like breast density and microbiome analysis; and lifestyle data (e.g., shopping habits, screen time, and school lunch consumption).

- **Financial Support and Resources:** Collaborating with companies can offer financial support and resources that go beyond public funding capabilities. This can expedite research and development processes facilitating market access to preventive solutions.
- **Execution:** Involvement from businesses, historically and today, plays a role in expanding successful public projects into widespread healthcare solutions. Their expertise in commercialising and distributing health technologies ensures that advancements in prevention can effectively reach various healthcare settings.

Gaps

Ensuring the privacy and security of health information is a concern, especially when private entities are involved. The development of data-driven healthcare tools necessitates collecting sensitive data, such as genetic, racial, and sexual orientation information, raising privacy, discrimination, and stigmatisation concerns. Additional data types, such as screen exposure and social interaction metrics (evaluating depth and frequency of social connections) also present challenges, especially regarding privacy. Furthermore, issues like inaccurate self-reporting and lack of standardised methods can introduce biases.⁷⁴

⁷⁴ Andrus, M., Spitzer, E., Brown, J. & Xiang, A. 'What We Can't Measure, We Can't Understand': Challenges to Demographic Data Procurement in the Pursuit of Fairness. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2011.02282> (2021); Bogen, M., Rieke, A. & Ahmed, S. Awareness in practice: tensions in access to sensitive attribute data for antidiscrimination. in Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency 492–500 (Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020). doi:10.1145/3351095.3372877.; El-Azab, S. & Nong, P. Clinical algorithms, racism, and "fairness" in healthcare: A case of bounded justice. *Big Data Soc.* 10, 20539517231213820 (2023).; Lee, S. S.-J., Fullerton, S. M., Saperstein, A. & Shim, J. K. Ethics of inclusion: Cultivate trust in precision medicine. *Science* 364, 941–942 (2019).; Kristiansen, T. B., Kristensen, K., Uffelmann, J. & Brandslund, I. Erroneous data: The Achilles' heel of AI and personalised medicine. *Front. Digit. Health* 4, (2022).

- Including sensitive attributes can promote fairness by reflecting diverse populations, despite GDPR restrictions requiring strict safeguards like pseudonymization and consent.⁷⁵ Balancing these regulatory constraints with the need for fairness through data inclusion is crucial for creating equitable and effective healthcare tools.
- Implementing data protection measures and establishing clear regulatory guidelines can help mitigate these risks. However, differences in standards across regions can challenge the smooth integration of new technologies. Aligning regulations and setting guidelines for prevention tools can promote better collaboration.

The secondary use of health data for personalised prevention faces significant regulatory challenges, including the fragmented application of GDPR rules across EU Member States which creates barriers for cross-border research.⁷⁶ The European Health Data Space (EHDS) proposal aims to harmonise the framework for primary and secondary use of health data, but raises concerns about individual control over data and the risk of bias if certain groups opt out.

Wearable devices like smartphones and smartwatches offer continuous, real-time health data crucial for developing personalised prevention tools, but their use raises regulatory concerns. Ensuring data validity,⁷⁷ and addressing the accessibility and privacy disparities associated with wearables, especially those producing continuous data, will require an aligned regulatory framework.⁷⁸ Data from wearables must meet high-quality standards and protect user privacy.

With regard to the private sector and PPPs making genetic tests available to patients across Europe, a number of regulatory considerations need to be assessed. This includes whether the EU Regulation on In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices provides adequately high standards of safety and

⁷⁵ Žliobaitė, I. & Custers, B. Using sensitive personal data may be necessary for avoiding discrimination in data-driven decision models. *Artif. Intell. Law* 24, 183–201 (2016).; Veale, M. & Binns, R. Fairer machine learning in the real world: Mitigating discrimination without collecting sensitive data. *Big Data Soc.* 4, 2053951717743530 (2017).; Forti, M. The Deployment of Artificial Intelligence Tools in the Health Sector: Privacy Concerns and Regulatory Answers within the GDPR New Voices. *Eur. J. Leg. Stud.* 13, 29–44 (2021).; van Bekkum, M. & Zuiderveen Borgesius, F. Using sensitive data to prevent discrimination by artificial intelligence: Does the GDPR need a new exception? *Comput. Law Secur. Rev.* 48, 105770 (2023).; Dwork, C., Hardt, M., Pitassi, T., Reingold, O. & Zemel, R. Fairness through awareness. in *Proceedings of the 3rd Innovations in Theoretical Computer Science Conference* 214–226 (Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2012). doi:10.1145/2090236.2090255.

⁷⁶ Slokenberga, S. Setting the Foundations: Individual Rights, Public Interest, Scientific Research and Biobanking. *GDPR Biobanking* 43, 11–30 (2020).

⁷⁷ Cho, S., Ensari, I., Weng, C., Kahn, M. G. & Natarajan, K. Factors Affecting the Quality of Person-Generated Wearable Device Data and Associated Challenges: Rapid Systematic Review. *JMIR MHealth UHealth* 9, e20738 (2021).

⁷⁸ Canali, S., Schiaffonati, V. & Aliverti, A. Challenges and recommendations for wearable devices in digital health: Data quality, interoperability, health equity, fairness. *PLOS Digit. Health* 1, e0000104 (2022).; Cheung, S. Disambiguating the benefits and risks from public health data in the digital economy. *Big Data Soc.* 7, 2053951720933924 (2020).

performance for genetic tests⁷⁹, and the impact of diverse legal requirements regarding medical supervision, genetic counselling and informed consent across European countries⁸⁰. In addition, other potential regulatory initiatives, such as self-regulation of the industry and patient education need to be explored.

Priorities and Implementation

- **Stakeholder Platforms:** Establishing platforms where stakeholders from the public sector institutions and academia can collaborate on prevention strategies promotes knowledge exchange, joint ventures and coordinated efforts toward common objectives. Moreover, arranging workshops and conferences to promote cooperation and knowledge exchange between public and private sectors builds up PPP networks. Additionally, it is essential to establish trust between institutions and private companies. Being transparent in communicating and involving stakeholders in decision-making processes can strengthen this trust and streamline cooperation. Establishing a culture of trust is paramount for patients and citizens to feel comfortable sharing their personal data, empowering them to become active participants in their own healthcare.
- **Regulatory Sandboxes:** These controlled environments allow for testing health technologies in various kinds of partnerships. This approach enables private companies to innovate while ensuring compliance with health regulations, expediting the introduction of solutions to the market.
- **Defining appropriate policies/regulations for the private sector.** Stakeholders should assess the impact of current regulations on the private sector and consider whether additional policies/regulations, such as educational initiatives or transparent advertising, could improve responsible test implementation. These initiatives should foster a responsible partnership and proactively address future challenges in personalised prevention approaches.
- **Encouraging Private Sector Engagement:** Implement detailed incentives such as tax benefits, funding opportunities or exclusive research collaborations to encourage private businesses to participate in personalised prevention plans. These incentives should be accompanied by

⁷⁹ Niemiec E, Kalokairinou L, Howard HC. (2017) Current ethical and legal issues in health-related direct-to-consumer genetic testing. *Per Med*;14(5):433-45.

⁸⁰ Kalokairinou L, Howard HC, Slokenberga S, Fisher E, Flatscher-Thoni M, Hartlev M, et al. (2018) Legislation of direct-to-consumer genetic testing in Europe: a fragmented regulatory landscape. *J Community Genet.*;9(2):117-32.

strong privacy protections to ensure data security. This can lead to development of health-promoting solutions integrated with individual data, like wearable devices, personalised nutrition, genomic testing services, and Direct-to-Consumer (DTC) products. The public sector must set guidelines for responsible marketing and verify the scientific validity, efficacy, and clinical utility of these products, ensuring their availability and presentation as options rather than necessities.

- **Framework for Evaluation:** Provision of specific indicators for the assessment of the successes of PPPs in personalised prevention. Proposition of a regular evaluation process to ensure consistent improvements.
- **Public Awareness and Education:** Utilise media, awareness campaigns, public forums and other methods to educate the public on the benefits and potential of personalised prevention through PPPs.

Considerations

Collaborating with the private sector may be beneficial in many ways to advancing prevention efforts. By encouraging innovation, providing resources, and ensuring solutions, private companies play a significant role in transforming preventive healthcare. Strategic partnerships, frameworks and a focus on ethical practices are vital for unlocking the full potential of this collaboration leading to more effective and personalised health outcomes. However, in dealing with PPP, the public sector should set up indicators for assessing the success of partnerships between the involved entities in personalised prevention enabling regular evaluation of their impact and efficacy.

Challenge 8: Access, Equity and Coverage

Status

Similar to other healthcare initiatives, testing in personalised prevention should aim to maximise benefits while minimising potential disadvantages. Benefits may extend beyond clinical outcomes to include social and psychological impacts⁴⁷. To fully realise the benefits of personalised prevention and fulfill the promise of universal health coverage in European healthcare systems, equitable access is a key challenge. Access can be defined through the 5As⁸¹: availability, affordability, accessibility

⁸¹<https://www.eu-patient.eu/news/latest-epf-news/2016/epf-position-paper-on-access-from-the-patients-perspective/>

(including geographic barriers), adequacy (including quality), and appropriateness (whether the service meets the needs of different population groups). Governments and health stakeholders must integrate these dimensions into personalised prevention strategies for successful implementation. Key elements include reimbursement, coverage of interventions, and integration into basic healthcare entitlements and routine preventive care to ensure availability and affordability.

Other factors impacting access to personalised prevention include lifestyle and behavioural modifications, awareness and understanding of personalised prevention, knowledge of family medical history, and availability of genetic information to inform disease risk understanding. These elements relate to health literacy and patient/citizen empowerment.

Population-based prevention strategies often fail to meet the specific needs of vulnerable groups. Lower income and socio-economic status, often affecting minority groups, are linked to reduced access to health information and healthcare, leading to poorer health outcomes. Personalised approaches can help reduce health inequalities by addressing individual needs based on environmental, behavioural, socio-economic, and cultural factors. However, access and equity considerations must be integrated into implementation strategies from the very start.

Gaps

Insufficient focus on impact and investment in prevention across sectors: Low health literacy is often associated with limited awareness of the determinants of health, leading to less healthy behaviours, decreased participation in screenings and vaccinations, and healthcare avoidance. Increased investment in health literacy can help address the knowledge gap in prevention, especially for vulnerable groups. Additionally, climate change exacerbates existing health inequities while creating new forms of disparity based on geographic location and social vulnerability. There is a need to move towards more integrated health services, based on a lifecourse approach and selection of services based on the holistic needs of a certain population.⁸² However, budget constraints across European countries may hinder the provision and reimbursement of additional health services, despite the potential long-term savings and improved health outcomes from preventive measures.

⁸² <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/primary-health-care-conference/linkages.pdf>

Limited utilisation of digital health technologies: Digital transformation in healthcare requires significant investment and is still in its early stages in many European countries. Access to digital health technologies is limited, especially for vulnerable groups at risk of digital exclusion, such as older people, socially excluded groups, people living in areas with limited internet coverage, etc.⁸³ The use of AI in healthcare poses challenges regarding health inequities, as algorithmic models often include errors and biases due to continuous under-representation of many ancestry groups in health datasets. Efforts to improve digital health literacy across the population are needed to build trust and understanding of health data collection and sharing.

Lack of harmonisation across Europe: Varying approaches to health data privacy, genetic testing, and insurance coverage mean that patients and citizens across Europe do not enjoy the same rights. Healthcare systems' management and organisation remain the sole competence of EU member states, with varying health budgets and priorities. As a result, inequalities within and between European countries in access to health and social services remain. More harmonised approaches and increased solidarity among member states could help close this gap and foster more equitable access.

Priorities and implementation

A paradigm shift is needed to integrate personalised prevention into healthcare systems and achieve universal access to personalised prevention interventions. Three key priorities can help address the gaps outlined above: policymaking, collaboration and partnership among stakeholders, and outreach and training for communities and stakeholders. They overlap with priorities on community outreach/engagement (Challenge 5) and capacity building (Challenges 5 and 6) which are elaborated above. Further complementary priorities for implementation are:

- *Policymaking:* Support the use of digital health technologies in healthcare while prioritising a regulatory environment which prevents discrimination and bias and safeguards citizens' control over their personal data. Health and social policies should be complemented by regulatory frameworks that protect against discrimination based on socio-economic status, health status, race and ethnicity, religion, gender identity and sexual orientation, etc.

⁸³ <https://www.england.nhs.uk/long-read/inclusive-digital-healthcare-a-framework-for-nhs-action-on-digital-inclusion/>

- *Policymaking*: Integrate preventive approaches into health systems and routine clinical practice, such as regular health checkups for the general population and better preventive counselling, providing adequate access to underserved communities and minorities. This includes integrating vulnerability mapping into health equity assessments , addressing geographic and cultural barriers to access to quality services, ensuring full coverage of relevant personalised preventive interventions by the national health insurance system, developing targeted interventions and reimbursement frameworks particularly for vulnerable populations, and earmarking funding for preventive health programmes, research, and infrastructure.
- *Collaboration and partnership*: Consider PPP with e.g. technology companies to develop and implement affordable digital health tools prioritising data security and privacy. Sustain the development and implementation of equitable personalised prevention interventions through diverse funding mechanisms and research programmes.
- *Outreach and training*: Prioritise awareness and health literacy programmes for the general public and patients about access to personalised prevention interventions. Specific efforts are needed to reach vulnerable populations through targeted/adapted messages and use of relevant media channels, including social media, television, radio, and community events.

Considerations

Integrating access and equity into the implementation of personalised prevention is essential to building citizens and patients' trust, a notion that is addressed across other aspects of relevance to this project, from the development of data collection tools and infrastructure to responsible research and innovation. Providing citizens and patients with accessible, affordable, appropriate, and high-quality personalised preventive care will help realise the potential of personalised prevention for improved health outcomes. This requires sustained investment, supported by potentially new funding approaches and evidence on the medium and long term cost-effectiveness of personalised prevention interventions.

Challenge 9: Ethical, Legal, Social Issues (ELSI)

Status

Advancements in genomic sequencing, extensive health data, and digital integration in healthcare have enabled personalised prevention through tailored risk profiles that analyse genetic, behavioural, and socio-economic factors. As personalised prevention evolves, research into ethical, legal, and social implications will be crucial.⁸⁴ ⁸⁵Current efforts address privacy concerns by strengthening data protection and giving individuals control over their health information. As mentioned earlier in the text, emerging regulatory frameworks like the European Health Data Space will shape the processing of health data for both primary and secondary purposes⁸⁶.

Gaps

Collaborative research will be essential to integrate ethical, legal, and social principles into personalised prevention, ensuring innovations are accessible and contribute to a fair and equitable healthcare system.

Priorities and implementation

- Informed consent

Informed consent tools will be essential for ensuring citizens and patients understand the benefits, risks, and implications of personalised prevention strategies. These tools should provide clear, accessible information about the nature of the tests, potential outcomes, and subsequent healthcare decisions while addressing privacy concerns and data security.

- Responsible testing

We must consider factors such as disease prevalence, disease severity, financial constraints, and future implications to properly determine the appropriateness of certain tests over others. Though

⁸⁴ Howard HC, Swinnen E, Douw K, Vondeling H, Cassiman JJ, Cambon-Thomsen A, et al. The ethical introduction of genome-based information and technologies into public health. *Public Health Genomics*. 2013;16(3):100-9.

⁸⁵ Borry P, Bentzen HB, Budin-Ljøsne I, Cornel MC, Howard HC, Feeney O, et al. The challenges of the expanded availability of genomic information: an agenda-setting paper. *Journal of Community Genetics*. 2018;9(2):103-16.

⁸⁶ Marelli L, Stevens M, Sharon T, Van Hoyweghen I, Boeckhout M, Colussi I, et al. The European health data space: Too big to succeed? *Health Policy*. 2023;135:104861.

these considerations vary among individuals, the public and private sectors must make thoughtful decisions to prioritise addressing the most important health problems and how to budget resources in proportion to other healthcare demands.

- Maintaining trust and delivering effective communication

To maintain public trust in personalised prevention, it is essential to implement safeguards against misuse (e.g. discrimination, etc.). Furthermore, effectively translating and communicating knowledge to all stakeholders will be crucial for realizing the full potential of personalised prevention.

- Building evidence

The implementation of new technologies and research findings faces significant challenges, including limited evidence of clinical utility, varying interpretations of benefits, institutional resistance, data integration issues, a need for improved clinician understanding and patient-centered ecosystems, etc. To successfully implement personalised prevention strategies and enhance healthcare outcomes, it is crucial to address these challenges, improve data sharing, and incorporate public perspectives.

- Ensuring data privacy

In personalised prevention, key concerns include ensuring privacy, maintaining database integrity, and regulating data sharing and data access for authorised users and allowed purposes. Standardising data formats, protecting against unauthorised access, and providing adequate storage and computational infrastructure are crucial for securely managing health information to advance prevention strategies effectively.

- Ensuring fair access

Ensuring fair access in personalised prevention requires equitable distribution of outcomes, balanced disclosure of sensitive attributes used to develop personalised prevention approaches, regulated commercial involvement, and fair distribution of potential benefits.

- Concerns regarding linking different sources of data

With increasing health data from personalised prevention, it is crucial to address the risks of cross-linking health information to derive new information about individuals. Robust guidelines are needed to ensure safety controls and protect sensitive patient information.

Considerations

To effectively integrate ELSI principles into practice, collaboration among researchers, healthcare providers, policymakers, industry leaders, and advocacy groups is crucial. Interdisciplinary research and dialogue can help develop comprehensive guidelines and frameworks that address these complex issues. This approach will enhance the ethical implementation of personalised prevention, build public trust, and ensure equitable access to advancements, ultimately promoting a fairer healthcare system.

Challenge 10: Changing behaviour

Status

For personalised prevention to reach its full potential, citizens and patients need to be aware of preventive options, and know how to take actions towards interventions or behaviour change to actually achieve prevention or better health. Increasingly, we are better able to personalize risk prediction for certain disorders, e.g. based on genetic information, but our understanding of behaviour change, and personalizing options for such change is limited. Merely providing information is not enough to influence behaviour. People may not understand the information, they may not be interested or motivated to change their behaviour, they may not feel confident or in control of their behaviour, or face actual barriers to behaviour change.

Social sciences, health sciences and behavioural sciences have focused on various aspects of interventions to change behaviour⁸⁷. Nudging behaviours has been shown to be effective in promoting healthy behaviour, for instance, in changing diet and smoking cessation. Nudging techniques include improving accessibility, adapting presentation of information and providing financial or emotional incentives for behaviour. Much research has focused on how to present risk information combining

⁸⁷ Nudging in Public Health Lifestyle Interventions: A Systematic Literature Review and Metasynthesis - PubMed (nih.gov)

written text and numerical presentation with visual presentations to people with varying degrees of health and digital literacy.

Gaps

The discussion on promoting behaviour change in personalised prevention takes place across the domains of public health and clinical genetics, each with their own traditions. Whereas in public health behaviour is stimulated when the outcome is seen as to be in the best interest of all (e.g. exercise), in genetics the emphasis has been on making an informed choice requiring counselling. This is particularly important when genetic information on a familial disorder has consequences for reproduction or in the case of invasive interventions such as preventive surgeries for hereditary cancers. In practice also in public health it is important to ensure informed consent, for instance for participating in screening programmes. On the other hand, patient decisions regarding new applications of personalised prevention, such as pharmacogenomics and lifestyle-related advice based on genetic susceptibility may be more similar to traditional public health approaches. More research is needed on acceptability, ethics and effectiveness of information and health-related choices in these cases. This also pertains to the influence on motivation of the context of being offered a test or tool by the healthcare system versus buying a direct-to-consumer (genetic) test or health device⁸⁸. Findings about consumers accessing e.g. cancer screening after receiving a test result may have been influenced by a prior interest in one's own health, underlying the purchase of such a test⁸⁹.

From the recent history of genetic testing we have learned that merely receiving genetic information on the risk to develop a disorder or susceptibility is not per se effective. About 40-50% of first-degree family members decide to have genetic testing themselves, after being informed about the diagnosis of an index patient in their family for monogenic subforms of common disorders, such as *BRCA*-related breast cancer, hereditary colon cancer or cardiovascular disorders. These first-degree family members have a 50% risk of having inherited the same pathogenic variant. Interventions have tried to increase uptake by a more pro-active role of health care professionals helping the patient to inform

⁸⁸ Nolan 2023 Clin Gen (review anclin validity consumer impact cons HCP exp att).pdf

⁸⁹ Models of communication for polygenic scores and associated psychosocial and behavioral effects on recipients: A systematic review – ScienceDirect

family members, while also digital tools for communicating information to family members have been introduced. Having an affected family member in these situations is nonetheless seen as an important incentive to seek out care. In the situation that less informative tests with lower risks are used for multifactorial disorders, without a family history, motivation for behaviour change or uptake of interventions may be low⁹⁰. In recent years studies have been conducted on behaviour change after receiving polygenic risk scores that indicate a relatively modest risk for a variety of disorders, suggesting some positive changes⁹¹ in adapting lifestyle, medication or screening, without increasing anxiety.

Implementation and priorities

Communicating personal risk information, such as gained via genetic tests, has the potential to stimulate healthy behaviour and prevention-related choices. It is important to better understand motivation for behaviour change by developing standards for best practices in communication of genetic information and of measuring relevant outcomes for behaviour change, such as uptake of screening, changing lifestyle, , et cetera⁹². To enhance the effectiveness of behaviour change interventions, individuals need to become aware of their personal objectives and feel confident it is possible to reach these. Behavioral interventions should help individuals to define clear, realistic and tailored behavioural goals, using the SMART framework (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound). Based on barriers, resources, and readiness or ability to change (e.g. through self-assessment tools or motivational interviewing), these goals could be adjusted.

For interventions to be effective various levels should be addressed and connected: the individual level and choices made, taking into account of the relevant (healthcare) context of the individual and their health needs and characteristics such as health literacy, the community level, and the societal level allowing for the accessibility of care and prevention via funding or regulation and public-private partnerships.

⁹⁰ Can Communicating Personalised Disease Risk Promote Healthy Behaviour Change? A Systematic Review of Systematic Reviews - PubMed (nih.gov)

⁹¹ Stewart KFJ 2018 J Comm Gen (review health beh resp psy impact follow-up Covolo).pdf

⁹² Models of communication for polygenic scores and associated psychosocial and behavioral effects on recipients: A systematic review - ScienceDirect

Considerations

In developing personalised prevention approaches, information and choice should be key cornerstones of promoting healthy behaviours, as behavioural interventions and encouragements should never be based on fear or force, and especially genetic risk information may be misunderstood. For instance a belief in genetic determinism may be connected to feelings of fatalism and reluctance to change behaviour, or overoptimism against changing lifestyle when perceived to be not at risk. The path forward aims to support citizens and patients in accessing and understanding information so they can make optimal health-related choices themselves, and help them sustain relevant behaviours..

4. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation, Acronym	Description
1+MG	1+Million Genomes
B1MG	Beyond 1 Million Genomes
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DCT	Direct-to-consumer testing
EGA	European Genome Phenome Archive
EP PerMed	European Partnership for Personalised Medicine
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure
GoE	Genome of Europe
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Studies
HIA	Health Impact Assessment

HTA	Health Technology Assessment
ICPerMed	International Consortium for Personalised Medicine
LEA	Essential Levels of Assistance
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
PDTA	Diagnostic Therapeutic Assistance Pathways
PPP	Public-private partnership
PRECeDI	PREvention of Chronic DIseases
PROPHET	A personalised Prevention Roadmap for the Future Healthcare
PROs	Patient-reported outcomes
PRS	Polygenic risk score
RCTs	Randomised controlled trials
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
THCS	Transforming Health and Care Systems

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ROPHET

a PeRsOnalized Prevention roadmap
for the future HEalThcare

PROPHET Roadmap

*** Priority level (goal):**

 Immediate : within 2 years

 Mid-term: within 5 years

 Long-term: within 10 years

**** Expected timeline (action):**

 Short term (1-3 years)

 Medium (4-6 years)

 Long-term (7-10 years)

The Roadmap for the “A Personalized Prevention roadmap for the future Healthcare” (PROPHET) Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)							
The broad scope of promotion and prevention (Challenge 1 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Strengthen governance of health determinants across sectors 	Support applied research and pilot projects across regions to test coordination models between health systems and other key sectors (e.g., environment, education, labor), engaging local authorities, healthcare providers, and academic institutions to integrate health and non-health	Multisectoral nature of determinants of health and disease	Benchmarking of best practices across sectors and countries	Research community, EU	One Health European Joint Programme (https://onehealth.ejp.eu/) Personalized CANcer Primary Prevention research through Citizen Participation and digitally enabled social innovation (4-PCAN) Project	EU calls	Inclusion of diverse determinants and sectors in research calls

	determinants in the policies 						
Balance awareness and investment between prevention and care </p>	Lack of incentives and resources to systematically integrate prevention in healthcare (Around 6% of health budgets to care across EU is currently spent on prevention)	<p>Research and Innovation investment in integrated prevention programmes</p> <p>Health benefits from preventive interventions not immediately observed, as outcomes from clinical care ones</p>	EU/ national/ regional/ local policymakers in collaboration with healthcare professionals, patients, citizens, researchers, civil society (to ensure funding programmes adequately meet population needs)	<p>Invest4Health project</p> <p>International Consortium of Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed)</p> <p>European Reference Network (ERNs) clinical care and expertise</p> <p>European Partnership for Personalized Medicine (EPPerMed)</p>	European Commission, national, regional, local funding (health budgets, research budgets, etc.)	<p>Percentage of research funding for prevention research</p> <p>Impact of funding programmes on health outcomes</p> <p>Availability of long-term plans for prevention funding at governmental level</p> <p>Number of scientific publications on prevention</p>	
Improving the scope of biomarkers used	Increase applied and clinical research on	Lack of accessible data on non-genetic	Identify new biomarkers that can be translated	Research community	European human exposome network ;	European Commission	Number of scientific publications

<p>in personalised primary prevention beyond genetics</p>	<p>biomarkers and their interactions for prevention.</p> <p>Lack of quality population-based data structures that can have enough power and quality to address this challenge (to collect and analyse information) (Medium)</p>	<p>into preventive interventions</p> <p>Explore gene-environment and other biomarker interaction that might conduct to clear preventive actions</p> <p>Create strong European infrastructures that integrate such complex and large volume data</p>	<p>Public Health organisations</p>	<p>Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals PARC;</p> <p>Exposome powered tools for healthy living in urban settings EXPANSE, Genome, Environment, Microbiome and Metabolome in Autism GEMMA & Oncobiome Projects;</p>	<p>(Horizon Europe, EU4Health)</p>	<p>reporting data on non-genetic biomarkers and their interactions</p> <p>Number of non-genetic biomarkers, and genetic and non-genetic interaction biomarkers assessed that can clearly improve and personalize preventive actions</p>	
<p>Harmonize health data sharing regulations across EU member states to enable equitable</p>	<p>Create a centralized platform to share best practices in personalized prevention and lessons learned</p>	<p>Fragmented governance, infrastructure, inequalities, and lack of regulation affects citizen trust</p>	<p>Increased policy alignment, interoperable systems, improved citizen trust and participation.</p>	<p>European Commission, national governments, Horizon Europe/EU4Health Programme</p>	<p>EHDS implementation; TEHDAS 1&2 eHealth network; GDPR implementation the context of</p>	<p>European Commission and National budgets, public-private partnerships.</p>	<p>Number of Member states actively participating in platform development and use</p>

access and collaboration 				1+Million Genome Initiative/Genome EDIC		Number of citizen and patient representatives participating in platform development	
Continuous evidence synthesis system supporting personalised prevention (Challenge 2 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Generate robust evidence on the clinical efficacy and broader impact of omics-based prevention approaches. 	Develop funding programmes for rigorous studies on clinical efficacy of personalised prevention approaches (e.g., Randomized Controlled Trial (RCTs)) Support research generating evidence on the cost-effectiveness of omics-based	Difficulty in conducting robust trials (e.g., RCTs) and collecting comprehensive data on clinical efficacy and broader impacts (e.g., cost-effectiveness, acceptability, feasibility) of omics-based prevention tests.	Conduction of studies on clinical efficacy of omics-based preventive approaches Valuation reports on cost-effectiveness, acceptability, and feasibility; Integration of the evaluation of patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), clinicians' feedback, or	Research community, EU and national funding agencies, clinical trial networks.	ICPerMed EP PerMed	Horizon Europe, EU4Health, national research budgets.	Number of funded studies on clinical efficacy of omics-based preventive approaches Number of cost-effective analyses of omics-based preventive approaches Number of trials including PROMs and stakeholders feedbacks Number of reports evaluating the

	<p>prevention approaches.</p> <p>-Incorporate assessments of patient acceptability and implementation feasibility into clinical trials.</p>		<p>mixed-method evaluations in current and new clinical trials.</p>				<p>broader impact of omics-based approaches</p>
<p>Ensure a robust and transparent governance system for continuous evaluation of evidence in personalised prevention</p>	<p>Ensuring the validity and transparency of the evidence evaluation process.</p>	<p>Biannual expert meetings, reviews and evidence curation process updates.</p>	<p>European Commission Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) in collaboration with national public health agencies.</p>	<p>ICPerMed EP PerMed ERNs for collaborative clinical expertise Member State Coordination Group on HTA (HTACG) International Consortium for integrative genomics prediction (INTERVENE)</p>	<p>European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health)</p>	<p>No. of assessments, revisions and updates to the evidence curation process by the expert panel</p>	
<p>Guarantee the availability of high-quality and up-to-date</p>	<p>Create an evidence curation team to manage and maintain a</p>	<p>Recruiting and training specialized staff (informatics,</p>	<p>Fully operational curation team with documented Standard</p>	<p>DG SANTE in close collaboration with the Expert</p>	<p>ICPerMed EP PerMed ERNs for</p>	<p>Initial funding through Horizon Europe or Digital Europe</p>	<p>No. of curated publications added per cycle Adherence to</p>

<p>curated evidence to support personalised prevention</p>	<p>genetic epidemiology, genomics experts) Developing standardized curation protocols and Quality Assessment measures Ensuring coordination with existing national/international efforts to prevent duplication of work</p>	<p>Operating Procedures (SOPs) Monthly/quarterly curation cycles (number of new references curated and validated) Quality metrics (e.g., inter-rater reliability) for curated data, published annually</p>	<p>Panel and national public health agencies</p>	<p>collaborative clinical expertise Member States (HTACG)</p>	<p>Programme; co-funding by participating member states and potential private/public partnerships</p>	<p>SOPs and QA metrics Publication of annual curation reports Satisfaction/feedback from Expert Panel members</p>	
<p>Establish a common European standard for assessing the clinical utility and applicability of omics-based personalised prevention approaches.</p>	<p>Ensuring that the evaluation of omics evidence is based on rigorous and transparent criteria.</p>	<p>Publication of omics evidence production and synthesis guidelines and classification framework.</p>	<p>European Commission, EMA, ECDC, BBMRI-ERIC, ELIXIR, EATRIS, ECRIN and ERN-EuroGen</p>	<p>EU Joint Actions on non-communicable diseases; EU best practices portal</p>	<p>European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health funding)</p>	<p>Framework document published.</p>	

<p>Enable timely access to synthesised evidence on personalised prevention for researchers, clinicians, and policymakers</p>	<p>Ensuring scalability and inclusivity of the evidence reporting, synthesis and classification system.</p>	<p>Operational platform with tiered classifications for omics tests.</p>	<p>European Commission Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) in collaboration with national public health agencies</p>	<p>EU Joint Actions on non-communicable diseases</p>	<p>European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health, national funding)</p>	<p>Number of omics tests classified and available.</p>	
<p>Support research capacity and knowledge, to promote evidence-based adoption of personalised prevention</p>	<p>Enhancing knowledge and skills for implementing omics-based prevention.</p>	<p>Number of workshops held, and participants trained.</p>	<p>ECDC, WHO-EURO, National Public Health Institutes</p>	<p>EP PerMed European Commission</p>	<p>European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health, COST actions national institutions)</p>	<p>Participant feedback and post-training/exchanges application rates.</p>	
<p>Ensure long-term accessibility and interoperability of curated</p>	<p>Establish a comprehensive, EU-wide digital repository for</p>	<p>Large volume of publications to screen.</p>	<p>Fully functional database pilot with thousands curated</p>	<p>DG SANTE in collaboration with national</p>	<p>ICPerMed EP PerMed</p>	<p>EU budget through Digital Europe / Horizon Europe/EU4Heal</p>	<p>No. of curated publications Initial pilot usage metrics Database</p>

evidence on personalised prevention across Europe. 	Variety of data formats and metadata standards. Maintenance of data quality.	references focusing on personalised prevention within 2 years and continued curation onwards	public health agencies.	European Health Data Space (EHDS) Horizon Europe ERNs Member State HTACG	th; co-funding by participating member states.	usage across member states	
The PROPHEt Framework implementation (Challenge 3 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Create a network in support of the implementation of evidence-based personalised prevention approaches. 	Diverse national bodies may lack a unified vision for personalized prevention Diverse legal and cultural contexts across EU Member States	Launch of the network "Vision & Scope" document, including initial goals & priorities Number of countries involved and partners agencies enrolled	European Commission (DG SANTE) National Ministries of Health and related agencies (national public health institutes, national HTA bodies, national HIA bodies where available) Network secretariat (once operational)	ICPerMed EP PerMed Transforming Health and Care Systems partnership (THCS) Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics platform (CAN.HEAL) project JA PCM	European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health) COST Action Co-financing by network partners	Number of signed partnership agreements between EC and national institutions in the established network	
Establish a governance	Conduct a governance	Unclear governance and	Publicly available	Commission-appointed legal	ICPerMed EP PerMed	European Commission	Feasibility report published

structure for the personalized prevention network. 	membership criteria can hinder sustainable collaboration	feasibility report Recommended legal status (consortium vs official EU body) Defined membership criteria and governance structure	experts National authorities' legal teams	THCS	(Horizon Europe, EU4Health) Co-financing by network partners	Governance model endorsed by majority of EU Member States	
Formalize the network's operational frameworks 	Need standardized documents to ensure clarity of roles and processes	Charter and MoU signed by at least 8 Member States Defined roles for Secretariat, Steering Committees, membership fees, etc.	Commission-appointed legal experts National authorities' legal teams	ICPerMed EP PerMed THCS	European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health) Co-financing by network partners	Official Charter ratified Number of Member States signing the MoU Governance structure published	
Secure long-term financial	Identify long-term financing (EU budget lines,	Reliance on short-term or project-based	Full-time staffed secretariat Multi-year	European Commission (DG SANTE, DG	ICPerMed EP PerMed	European Commission	Secretariat's annual financial report

sustainability for the network. 	funding threatens sustainability	funding plan endorsed by 8 Member States Publicly available budget & resource allocation processes	Research) Member States (co-funding)		(Horizon Europe, EU4Health) Co-financing by network partner	Approved operating budget	
Strengthen multi-stakeholder engagement in personalized prevention strategies. 	Balancing interests of different stakeholders. Ensuring robust but feasible consultation	Stakeholder advisory committee(s) operational. Public consultations on personalized prevention guidelines/reports.	Secretariat National ministries of health DG SANTE	Large multi-stakeholders' initiatives in personalized/precision medicine at EU and national level	European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health) Co-financing by network partners Contribution by industry stakeholders	Frequency of stakeholder meetings and feedback Integration of stakeholder inputs into the network outputs like HTAs reports or other reports on the implementation of PP approaches. final outputs	
Integrate the main recommendations	Surveying national prevention	Harmonize the heterogeneous processes for	A report comparing existing processes across	Network Secretariat National public health agencies	ICPerMed EP PerMed THCS	Horizon Europe, EU4Health, Member State budgets	Published comparative report on prevention

<p>for evaluating personalized prevention approaches using the PROPHET Framework, into national standard procedures.</p>	<p>evaluating and implementing prevention proposes, within which the use of the PROPHET framework must be adapted and integrated.</p>	<p>Member States Identification of key touchpoints for integrating PROPHET Framework principles in national workflows</p>				<p>governance and managements in Member States. Number of Member States providing data on prevention governance and implementation mechanisms. Policy recommendations on how/where to integrate PROPHET framework in national personalised prevention processes</p>	
<p>Test the adaptability of the PROPHET Framework in real-world settings.</p>	<p>Promote & Pilot the PROPHET Framework in Multiple Countries to evaluate how it can be embedded in the development of national prevention programs</p>	<p>Need real-world testing & demonstration of the framework's adaptability in diverse healthcare settings</p>	<p>Pilot-specific policy briefs documenting lessons learned Feedback loop to refine local implementation guidance</p>	<p>Network Secretariat National public health agencies</p>	<p>ICPerMed EP PerMed THCS EU Joint Action PreventNCD JA PCM</p>	<p>Horizon Europe, EU4Health, Member State budgets</p>	<p>Pilot evaluation reports & policy briefs Adjusted, improved PROPHET implementation guidelines</p>

Define metrics to assess the social impact of personalized preventive approaches. 	Measuring social impact in a comprehensive and meaningful way, addressing diverse societal concerns.	Published social impact assessment tools, increased use of these tools in evaluating personalised prevention initiatives.	Network Secretariat consulting social scientists, public health experts, epidemiologist, regulatory bodies, civil society	ICPerMed EP PerMed THCS	EU grants, public health budgets	Number of assessment properly evaluating the social impact of personalized preventive approaches.	
Establish the PROPHET Framework as a guiding principle in national policy 	Every country has various processes in place for evaluating and implementing prevention programs, within which the use of the PROPHET framework must be adapted and integrated.	Formal adoption in at least 8 Member States (policy statements, guidelines).	Network Secretariat National public health agencies		EU4Health, Member State budgets	Number of Member States with formal adoption Inclusion of PROPHET principles in national guidelines for design and implementation of prevention programs.	

<p>Improve monitoring in personalized prevention</p>	<p>Lack of standardized guidance for tracking outcomes, cost-effectiveness, and equity impact in personalized prevention leads to inconsistent or incomplete monitoring.</p>	<p>Common metrics and data-collection protocols</p>	<p>Network Secretariat National public health agencies</p>	<p>ICPerMed EHDS</p>	<p>EU4Health, Member State budgets</p>	<p>Number of Member States formally developing guidelines Annual reports for data collection and analysis</p>	
<p>Build capacity in national institutions for better integration of the PROPHET Framework.</p>	<p>Diversity in methods, implementation strategies and training among different partners</p>	<p>Improved capacity among national stakeholders (health authorities, policymakers, etc.) to apply HTA and HIA in personalised prevention</p>	<p>Network Secretariat Academic partners & professional societies</p>	<p>ICPerMed</p>	<p>EU4Health, Member State budgets</p>	<p>Number of trained professionals Pre- and post-training surveys (to gauge knowledge gain) Uptake of HTA/HIA methods in Member States' prevention program guidelines Number of training sessions held (online/offline)</p>	

Stimulate research on impacts of personalized prevention approaches 	Equity impacts and patient acceptability are often overlooked; insufficient data hinders policy decisions and real-world adoption of personalized prevention.	Priority setting and funding opportunities	European Commission (DG SANTE, DG RTD) Network Secretariat (advisory role) Academic and other research institutions NGOs	ICPerMed EP PerMed JA PCM	– Horizon Europe, EU4Health Co-funding by industry Co-funding by nonprofit research foundations	Number of funded research projects focusing on equity & acceptability Peer-reviewed publications & policy briefs	
Data collection and integration, and Data Infrastructure (Challenge 4 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Standardise data structure across research and healthcare sectors. 	Develop and implement harmonised data standards for genomic, clinical, wearable, relevant environmental, and socioeconomic data, in collaboration with research	Fragmentation of data standards including inconsistent data formats, variability in storage, and different terminologies Resistance to change	A unified set of standards for data management across EU healthcare and research systems. Compliance across different countries resulting in accessible data for all	European Commission (including funded initiatives and projects: https://gdi.onemil.liongenomes.eu https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes	- Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) - 1+Million Genomes Initiative (1+MG) - HealthData@EU Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS 1&2)	European Commission, National Health & Research Budgets, Research Infrastructures	Percentage of organisations adopting standardised practices for genomic, clinical, wearable, relevant environmental, and socioeconomic data.

	<p>communities and organisations such as Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) and International Standards Organisation (ISO)</p>	<p>Differences in implementations of the standard across borders due to differences in data governance on a national level</p> <p>Technological barriers on the use of infrastructures hosting data which might result not being accessible by everyone in health care or research</p> <p>It is also challenging to educate healthcare providers and researchers to implement the standards</p>	<p>Data quality standards will be better resulting in improved data analysis, thus safer, and maybe faster conclusions and results for patients, thus better precision and possible prevention</p> <p>Better data translation from research to medicine and alignment of data exchange</p>	<p>EHDS Research Infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR) Standards setting organisations such GA4GH and ISO</p>	<p>International consortium for integrative genomics prediction (INTERVENE) -Next generation tools for genome-centric multimodal data integration in personalized cardiovascular medicine (NextGen)</p>		<p>Number of datasets compliant with the adopted standards.</p> <p>Number of publications citing the infrastructure or the data standards</p>
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<p>Enhance data discovery, accessibility and quality of genomic and health data.</p>	<p>-Inconsistent metadata practices and fragmentation of resources and efforts.</p> <p>Researchers, healthcare professionals might not be able to adopt the standards</p>	<p>Standardised metadata practices adopted across EU repositories to improve data cataloguing.</p> <p>Increased discoverability and usage rates of genomic and health datasets in research and clinical applications.</p>	<p>Funding organisations such as the European Commission, Research Infrastructures, and Academic Research Institutions.</p>	<p>GDI, 1+MG, HealthData@EU</p>	<p>European Commission, National Research Budgets, Research Infrastructures</p>	<p>Percentage increase in the discoverability and usage of genomic and health datasets.</p> <p>Adoption rates of metadata standards across EU repositories.</p>	
<p>Integration of different data types: genomic, clinical, lifestyle, relevant environmental, and socioeconomic data</p>	<p>Heterogeneity of Data: Genomic, clinical, socioeconomic, relevant environmental, behavioural, and lifestyle data vary significantly in structure, quality, and context.</p> <p>Technical Barriers: Lack of interoperable tools and</p>	<p>Increased research outputs using multi-sectoral integrated datasets.</p>	<p>European Commission, Research Infrastructures, Standards setting organisations</p>	<p>HealthData@EU</p> <p>Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI)</p>	<p>National Health Research Budgets, European Commission, Research Infrastructures,</p>	<p>Percentage of multisectoral datasets successfully integrated.</p> <p>Number of tools developed to support data integration.</p>	

		platforms to facilitate seamless integration across data types.					
<p>Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) models for personalised prevention.</p>	<p>Lack of necessary infrastructure, such as cloud-based storage, federated learning systems, and real-time data processing capabilities.</p> <p>Clinician training as healthcare professionals lack the necessary training to interpret and apply AI/ML models effectively in clinical practice.</p> <p>Security risks</p> <p>Cost</p>	<p>Increased adoption of AI/ML tools in clinical settings for prevention</p> <p>Increased capacity for analytics</p>	<p>Healthcare IT providers, Research institutions</p>	<p>Digital Cognitive Biomarker; LETHE project, Watching the Risk Factors: Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Prevention of Chronic Conditions (WARIFA) Brain Health Tool Box: Facilitating personalized decision-making for effective dementia prevention</p>	<p>European Commission, National Research Budget, Academic Research institutions.</p>	<p>Number of clinician-friendly tools deployed</p> <p>Increase in AI/ML-driven personalised prevention applications.</p>	
Improve the quality of	Provide logistical and structural	Ensuring the availability &	Cohort Hub with personal and	European Commission	ICPerMed	European Commission	Access core data (common or

evidence for personalised prevention through fostering of high-quality availability data for research beyond genomic information 	maintenance of high-quality population-based data for research to produce robust evidence for personalised prevention	technical resources	Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) and DG research in collaboration with national funding agencies.	1+MG , Genome of Europe	(Horizon Europe, EU4Health) and member states	federated) from main European cohorts with compatible data on environmental exposures, social determinants of health, clinical data and genetic and non-genetic biomarkers	
Community Engagement and trust (Challenge 5 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Actively engage citizens and patients in personalised prevention Policies 	Each EU country should have a task force to oversee citizen and patients representatives Ministers of EUMSs where personalised prevention policies are designed	Citizens are more difficult to engage than patients	Recognizable representative of patients/ public in personalised prevention initiatives	Governments, health care funders, professional organisations who develop personalised prevention policies; patient organisations and civil society organisations	ERNs for genomics / rare diseases 4P-CAN JANE2 EUnetCCC JA-PCM	EU via research funding, national funding bodies through e.g. partnerships with patient organisations and civil society organisations	Number of personalized prevention initiatives with recognizable engagement of citizens

Prioritise and improve community engagement 	Engagement has to start before people are affected	Patient organization or community groups involved in personalised prevention initiatives	Governments, health care funders, professional organisations who offer or develop personalised prevention policies, patient organisations and civil society organisations	ERNs for genomics / rare diseases Genome, Environment, Microbiome & Metabolome in Autism: an integrated multi-omics systems biology approach to identify biomarkers for personalized treatment and primary prevention of Autism Spectr (GEMMA)	EP PerMed THCS	Number of patient organization or community groups involved in personalised prevention initiatives	
Generate more structural funding for citizen and patient engagement in research, care and public	Generate funding for citizens/ patients in each personalised prevention Initiative 	Measures to evaluate engagement need to be streamlined	High percentage of personalised prevention initiatives with citizen/ patient engagement at higher IAP2 levels.	Governments or insurance companies who organize health care offers Fundors of research,	ERNs for genomics / rare diseases	EU via research funding, national funding bodies, foundations	Number of funded personalised prevention initiatives with citizen/ patients engagement

health, and their governance 							% of engagement level (IAP2)
<p>Education and raising awareness of options for personalised prevention and taking part in health research. Develop and study online information and communication tools </p>	<p>(Online) tools need to be accessible for people with low digital literacy and health literacy Family members need to be targeted Family members and healthy citizens in general are usually not approached by health care professionals</p>	<p>Tools to inform citizens, patients and research participants that are understandable and accessible also for persons with low (health) literacy; that can offer more information upon request (layered) Tools to inform healthy family members of patients with a genetic disorder Health research projects with accessible awareness options. Personalised prevention</p>	<p>Governmental agencies who develop (online) tools to inform patients and public. Funders of research. Governments, health care funders, professional organisations Funders of research</p>	<p>ERNs for genomics / rare diseases</p>	<p>National health budgets European Commission (Horizon Europe, EU4Health, national funding)</p>	<p>Number of tools that have specific low literacy version Number of tools to inform family members Percentage of health research projects with accessible awareness options Number of publications on the evaluation of these tools</p>	

			tools for family members and healthy citizens Publications on the evaluation of these tools				
Increase health literacy, especially among young populations 	Differences in health literacy leading to inequalities regarding access to and participation in healthcare and health outcomes	- Availability of tool(kits) for education on prevention - Exchange of best practices among involved stakeholders - Increased number of routine health check-ups - Higher vaccination rates	Wide range of stakeholders in health system and education system (government, public health authorities, education authorities, schools, civil society...)	- Schools4Health project about prevention and health literacy in schools - EU Health in Education: Transversal Projects to enable teachers to increase health literacy of school children	EU, national, regional, local sources (health budget, council funding, education budget, etc.) Funding source and scheme may vary between countries.	- Number of programmes implemented - Number of types of stakeholders involved in programmes - Number of participants (e.g. no. of schools) - Ratio of funding for health prevention programmes compared to other educational programmes	
Increase health literacy, especially among vulnerable populations 	Design and implement educational programmes for adults (especially minority and vulnerable groups) to	Differences in health literacy leading to inequalities regarding access to and participation in	Availability of tool(kits) for education on prevention Exchange of best practices among involved stakeholders	Wide range of stakeholders in health system and education system (government, public health authorities,	- 'Prevention in Action' project to increase health literacy on NCDs among population, including vulnerable	EU, national, regional, local sources (health budget, council funding, education budget, etc.) Funding source and	Number of programmes implemented Number of types of stakeholders involved in programmes

	normalise regular health check-ups and inform about prevention 	healthcare and health outcomes	Increased number of routine health check-ups Higher vaccination rates	education authorities, schools, civil society,...)	populations RISE-Vac project to increase vaccination uptake and health literacy among prison population Action grants given under the EU Joint Action PreventNCD since some of them focus on vulnerable groups and groups of low socioeconomic status	scheme may vary between countries	Number of participants (e.g. no. of institutions/organisations providing education) Ratio of funding for health prevention programmes compared to other educational programmes
Increase public engagement and participation in the development and implementation of personalised prevention 	Ensuring meaningful and inclusive participation from all stakeholders.	Increased public awareness and involvement, policies and strategies that reflect public concerns and values.	Public health organizations, research institutions, patient advocacy groups/organisations, civil society organisations.		EU grants, public health budgets	Number of public engagement activities, level of stakeholder participation, survey results on public awareness and satisfaction.	
Health Professionals and Policy Makers involvement (Challenge 6 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with	Funding sources	Output indicator

	Timeline for the implementation **)				the same objective		
Education on HTA/HIA with special reference to economic evaluations of personalised prevention Approaches 	Few experts in EU members states.	Number of training modules	Academia (experts in economic modelling)	Healthcare- and pharmaco-economics in support of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (HEcoPerMed)	EU grants, national HTA bodies	Number of training modules	
Appropriate training of non-genetic health care professionals for efficient stratification that include 'omics in public health screening 	Limited interest	Availability of training modules with large numbers of participants	Genetic health care professionals, public health care professionals, EUPHA	European Union of Medical Specialists (UEMS) NHS Genomics education Programme Global Genomics Network in Education and Training (GGNET)	National and international professional organisations	Number of training modules, number of participants	
Introduction of new methods for assessing practical competences aimed at the application of	Include Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) in training for personalised prevention	Assessment often focuses on knowledge, what is needed is also focus on applying knowledge and know-how in	Assessment including know-how	Organizations of genetic health care professionals, public health care professionals, EUPHA	European Board of Medical Geneticss (EBMG)	EU and national research grants on educational research	Number of assessment schemes including know-how

personalised prevention strategies 	addition to know-what						
Incorporation of public and patient involvement in education for health professionals 	Training and education is often developed top-down	Personalised prevention training modules that incorporated public and patients' input	Organizations of genetic health care professionals, public health care professionals, EUPHA, patient organisations and civil society organisations	ERNs for genomics/ rare diseases Innovative Health Initiative	EU and national research grants on educational research	Number of PP training modules that incorporated public and patients' input	
Regulatory aspects and synergy with the private sector (Challenge 7 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Foster effective public-private partnerships (PPPs) to advance personalised prevention strategies through innovation and resource sharing.	Establish stakeholder platforms and workshops for collaboration between public institutions, academia, and the private sector 	Building trust between stakeholders, including patients and citizens, to encourage data sharing and collaboration.	Creation of functional stakeholder platforms engaging a wide range of participants. Measurable increase in PPP-driven initiatives	National Governments, European Commission, and Private sector. Academic and Healthcare Institutions	Personalised Relapse Prediction (PARADISE) project	European Commission, Public Private Partnerships/Grants	Number and diverse types of stakeholders engaged Increase in collaborative PPP projects

		<p>Addressing differences in operational priorities and practices between public and private entities, including funding sources and sustainability.</p>	<p>and projects in personalised prevention</p> <p>Improved Data access and sharing due to collaborations that results in better technological advances improving prediction models.</p>				
<p>Promote innovation in personalised prevention by leveraging the technological expertise of private sector partners.</p>	<p>Encourage private-sector engagement through incentives for example tax benefits, funding opportunities, and exclusive research collaborations.</p> <p>Leverage EU funding to support innovation in</p>	<p>Balancing the need for innovation with stringent privacy and security requirements for sensitive health data.</p> <p>Addressing accessibility disparities in wearable technologies</p> <p>Ensuring that commercialised</p>	<p>Increased private-sector investments in personalised prevention technologies.</p> <p>Development and market introduction of validated, patient-centric health technologies</p> <p>Unified regulatory</p>	<p>-Private Sector Entities: Innovate and co-develop solutions.</p> <p>- Regulatory Bodies: Design and monitor regulatory sandboxes.</p> <p>Research Institutions: Collaborate on validation and testing.</p>	<p>Cancer Image Europe (EUCAIM)</p>	<p>European Commission (EU-Horizon Europe), private-sector Research and Development funding, public-private partnerships.</p>	<p>Number of innovative products developed and validated.</p> <p>Volume of private-sector investments in personalised prevention</p> <p>No of projects involved as a</p>

	<p>wearable devices, genomic technologies, and data integration tools for prevention efforts</p>	<p>products meet safety and performance standards, and ethical standards.</p>	<p>guidelines for personalised prevention across EU Member States.</p> <p>Increased collaboration agreements & strategic partnerships resulting in attracting more funding and into technological advancements.</p>				<p>results of partnership</p> <p>Adoption rate of standardized data frameworks and successful interoperability integrations</p>
<p>Strengthen public-private collaborations to accelerate the adoption of personalised prevention technologies.</p>	<p>Launch an EU platform for regular dialogue between regulators, founders, researchers, and private sector stakeholders, with incentives such as tax-deductible contributions for industry associations, and share knowledge</p>	<p>Enhance PPP to advance personalised prevention technologies</p>	<p>A functional platform with hybrid biannual meetings, opportunities and policy recommendations</p>	<p>EC in partnership with national authorities and industry companies and associations.</p>	<p>Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)</p>	<p>EU grants, industry contributions by tax benefits</p>	<p>Number of meetings held; number of actionable policy recommendations . Private companies /industry/ researchers and national health authorities satisfaction survey results.</p>

	for new products development 						
Harmonize regulatory standards across the EU to facilitate private sector innovation in personalised prevention complying with GDPR , EHDS and ethical principles. 	Regulatory environments that hinder innovation through personalised prevention Regulatory frameworks struggle to keep pace with rapid advancements in digital health technologies, delaying market adoption.	EU-wide harmonized guidelines for regulatory approval of personalised prevention products and solutions including AI use in development and update of the product.	EMA and national regulatory authorities and PROPHET consortium as consultant.	Digital Europe	EU grants, industry contributions by tax benefits	Number of harmonized regulatory documents published. Number of recommendations on personalised prevention published. - Number of new products, solutions for personalised prevention approved in a 10 year period. Private companies and national health authorities satisfaction survey results.	
Access, Equity and Coverage (Challenge 8 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator

<p>Ensuring sustained investment in prevention programmes</p>	<p>Lack of incentives and resources to systematically integrate prevention in healthcare (and encourage a paradigm/cultural shift from care to prevention)</p>	<p>Increased uptake of prevention measures among entire population, including children and vulnerable groups (higher number of check-ups, vaccination rates, etc.)</p> <p>Increased involvement of patients/ citizens (in research, design of funding schemes, etc.)</p>	<p>EU/ national/ regional/ local policymakers in collaboration with health care professionals, patients, citizens, researchers, civil society (to ensure funding programmes adequately meet population needs)</p>		<p>EU, national, regional, local funding (health budgets, research budgets, etc.)</p>	<p>Number of new funding programmes for prevention (research, etc.)</p> <p>Comparative budget amounts for prevention programmes over time</p> <p>Impact and reach of funding programmes, determined through evaluations</p> <p>Availability of long-term plans for prevention funding at governmental level</p> <p>Number of scientific publications on prevention including patient/citizen participation</p>	
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<p>Citizen access to, understanding of, and trust in digital health technologies</p>	<p>Trust – regulatory frameworks to ensure equitable and ethical data sharing to common principles that support patient privacy</p> <p>Access –ensuring analogue alternatives, accessibility through different platforms, understanding of national/regional/local characteristics, and personal choice to disengage from digital health technologies</p> <p>Understanding and trust – educational programmes and engagement activities</p>	<p>Health inequalities arising from access to digital technologies or from inherent biases within the technologies. Poor patient engagement in healthcare due to lack of trust in technologies; integration of health data use in HC/personalised prevention practice</p>	<p>Citizen engagement with digital healthcare technologies, to support general health management (staying healthy) and healthcare interventions when unwell.</p>	<p>Governments and health systems; patient and other civil society organisations; technology developers</p>	<p>GDPR; European Health Data Space/ eHDSI/ TEHDAS, AI act, EU Medical devices regulations; standardisation activities; EU action plan on the cybersecurity of hospitals and HC providers; eHealth network</p>	<p>Integrated with costs for implementing Personalised Prevention programmes – government level funding.</p>	<p>Proportion of citizens who engage with digital health technologies. (E.g. population surveys of use and views on technology)</p>
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Ensure fair and equitable access to personalised prevention 	Risk of unequal access to benefits	Balanced and transparent distribution of benefits resulting from personalised prevention approaches	Governments, regulatory bodies, healthcare providers, research funders	Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS & TEHDAS2)	EU and national funding	Number of equity and access assessment reports	
Ethical, Legal, Social Issues (Challenge 9 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
Strengthen public trust and prevent discrimination in personalised prevention 	Risk of discrimination and stigmatization, public concerns over data privacy	Increased public awareness, improved trust in personalised prevention	Governments, healthcare funders, researchers, patient advocacy groups	Beyond One Million Genomes (B1MG) SafePolyMed	EU and national funding	Number of public awareness initiatives and engagement activities	
Ensure data protection and responsible use of health data	Implement regulations on data sharing,	Risk of unlawful data processing, maintaining database integrity	Strengthened data protection and security measures	Data Protection Agencies, Health Data Access Bodies, Data	HealthData@EU , Cancer Image Europe (EUCAIM),	EU and national funding	Compliance with data protection frameworks

			<p>Access Committees</p>	<p>European Health Data Evidence Network (EHDEN)</p> <p>HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integratIon for the guT-bRain interplay (HEREDITARY)</p>			
<p>Harmonize health data sharing rules and support equitable access across EU member states</p>	<p>Fragmented governance, infrastructure, inequalities, and lack of citizen trust affect harmonization.</p>	<p>Increased policy alignment, interoperable systems, improved citizen trust and participation.</p>	<p>European commission, national governments, Horizon Europe/EU4Health Programme</p>	<p>EHDS implementation; TEHDAS 1&2 eHealth network; GDPR implementation</p>	<p>EU and National budgets, public-private partnerships.</p>	<p>No. of successful pilots</p> <p>No. of citizens and patients engaged in pilots</p> <p>No. of Member states adopting standards</p> <p>No. of financial support initiatives</p>	

<p>Address risks of linking different data sources</p>	<p>Potential privacy breaches and misuse of data</p>	<p>Ethical and legal framework for responsible data linkage</p>	<p>EU regulators</p>	<p>Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS & TEHDAS2), European Health Data Evidence Network (EHDEN) SHAIPED Better Project</p>	<p>EU and national funding</p>	<p>Number of established guidelines and regulatory frameworks for secure data linkage adopted at national and EU levels.</p>	
<p>Promote international collaboration to address ethical, legal, and social issues in personalised prevention</p>	<p>Coordinating efforts across different legal and regulatory frameworks, managing cross-border data sharing, and aligning research priorities.</p>	<p>Established international research consortia, increased cross-border collaborations, and shared ELSI frameworks.</p>	<p>International research organizations, governments, academic institutions.</p>	<p>Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)</p>	<p>International research grants, EU funding programs</p>	<p>Number of international collaborations, joint research publications, shared ELSI guidelines.</p>	
<p>Establish ethical guidelines for the use of emerging technologies in personalised prevention</p>	<p>Create a multidisciplinary task force to develop guidelines addressing the ethical implications of technologies such as AI, genomics, and</p>	<p>Keeping pace with rapid technological advancements and ensuring guidelines are comprehensive and up-to-date.</p>	<p>Published ethical guidelines, increased adherence to ethical standards in technology use.</p>	<p>Ethics committees, technology developers, regulatory bodies.</p>	<p>Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS & TEHDAS2) EP PerMed</p>	<p>International research grants, EU funding programs</p>	<p>Number of guidelines published, compliance rate.</p>

	digital health tools 						
Ensure that public-private partnerships in personalised prevention adhere to high ethical standards. 	Balancing commercial interests with ethical considerations and public good.	Increased adherence to ethical standards in public-private partnerships.	Regulatory bodies, industry associations, patient organisations, civil society organisations	Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS & TEHDAS2) IDERHA	EU funding programs, private sector investment	Compliance rate among public-private partnerships.	
Behavior challenge (Challenge 10 of SRIA)							
Goal (Priority level*)	Action (Expected Timeline for the implementation **)	Obstacle	Outcome	Responsible for the action	Other EU initiatives with the same objective	Funding sources	Output indicator
More research is needed on acceptability, ethics and effectiveness of information and health-related choices regarding	Research on acceptability, ethics and effectiveness of information and health-related choices on pharmacogenomi	Fields of public health, genetics and pharmacy are different pillars Communicating the risk is not	Publications on acceptability and effectiveness of health information based on personal omic information	Academia Funders of research Regulators EMA	Implementation of Personalized risk stratification for cancer and other NCDs - JA PreventNCD	COST action EU and national research grants	Number of publications

<p>pharmacogenomics and lifestyle-related advice based on genetic susceptibility</p>	<p>sufficient to change behavior</p> <p>Joining data from various sources is challenging and potentially over-regulated</p>						
<p>Understanding the influence on motivation of the context of being offered a test or tool (e.g. commercial versus healthcare system)</p>	<p>Communicating the risk is not sufficient to change behavior</p>	<p>Publications on (motivation for) behaviour change</p>	<p>Academia</p> <p>Funders of research</p>	<p>Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects and Implications of Direct-to-Consumer Genetic Testing ELSAIDTCGT </p>	<p>EU and national research grants</p>	<p>Number of publications</p>	
<p>Personalized prevention should target non-affected family members of affected individuals</p>	<p>Inform family members at high risk and motivate them for behaviour change</p> <p>Some countries forbid passing genetic information to relatives, even next-of-kin</p>	<p>Modules to inform family members</p>	<p>Public health, Academia, Professionals from organisations who offer or develop personalised prevention policies, ESHG, Regulators, lawmakers, Patient advocacy groups</p>	<p>Can.Heal Building the EU genomics platform</p>	<p>add EU and national research grants</p>	<p>Number of modules to inform family members</p> <p>Implementing or improving regulation</p>	

<p>Personalised prevention should integrate polygenic risk scores (PRS) where and when clinically utility has been proven</p>		<p>Assessment of PRS or integrated risk prediction tools disease prediction in disease prevention</p>	<p>Academia Funders of research Professional medical organizations (ESHG, ASHG)</p>	<p>Can.Heal Building the EU genomics platform</p>	<p>EU and national research grants</p>	<p>Number of publications on clinical utility of specific PRSs (integrated in combined risk modules)</p>	
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List of acronyms and abbreviations

European Union (EU)

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

European Reference Networks (ERNs)

Member State Coordination Group on HTA (HTACG)

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)

Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs)

Personalized CANcer Primary Prevention research through Citizen Participation and digitally enabled social innovation (4-PCAN)

International Consortium of Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed)

European Reference Network (ERNs)

European Partnership for Personalized Medicine (EP PerMed)

Member State Coordination Group on HTA (HTACG)

International Consortium for integrative genomics prediction (INTERVENE)